

Report D1.7
"OntoCommons
Standardisation Impact Report v2"

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Report D1.7

"OntoCommons Standardisation Impact Report v2"

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List of Acronyms

Item	Description
ATB	Institut für angewandte Systemtechnik Bremen GmbH
BFO	Basic Formal Ontology
CEN	European Committee for Standardisation
CENELEC	Comité Européen de Normalisation Électrotechnique
CNR	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche
CSAs	Coordination and Support Actions
CWA	CEN Workshop Agreement
DOLCE	Descriptive Ontology for Linguistic and Cognitive Engineering
DOME4.0	Digital Open Marketplace Ecosystem
EAB/EAG	External Advisory Board/Expert Advisory Group
EMMO	European Materials Modelling Council
ENIT	École Nationale d'Ingénieurs de Tarbes
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
e-SDF	E-SCIENCE DATA FACTORY
ESO	European Standard Organisation

ESS	European Standardisation System
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
EUOS	EU Observatory for ICT Standardisation, aka the Standards Observatory.
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
GCL	Goldbeck Consulting Ltd
ICF	Industry Commons Foundation
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
iiRDS	Intelligent Information Request and Delivery Standard
ISO	International Organisation for Standardisation
JRC	Joint Research Centre
MODA	Multimedia Ontology Driven Architecture
MSP	Multi-Stakeholder Platform
NMBP	Nanotechnologies, Advanced Materials, Biotechnology, and Advanced Manufacturing and Processing
OCES	OntoCommons Ontology EcoSystem
OSS	Open-Source Software
OWL	Web Ontology Language
RDA	Research Data Alliance
RIA	Research and Innovation Action
SAREF	Smart Applications REference
SDO	Standard Developing Organisation
TC	Technical Committee
TWG	Technical Working Group
UIBK	Universität Innsbruck
UiO	Universitetet i Oslo
UPM	Universidad Politecnica de Madrid
W3C	World Wide Web Consortium
WGs	Working Groups
WP	Work Package

Keywords

Standardisation, Materials, Manufacturing, Digital Industrial Transition, Cooperation, Harmonisation, Interoperability, Ontologies, Framework.

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Executive Summary

This report, D1.7, is the second iteration of the OntoCommons Standardisation Impact report (D1.6). Its objective is to describe the results and impacts achieved by OntoCommons in promoting the cooperation of the overall community on the standardisation of data across two fundamental industrial domains: materials and manufacturing.

The relevance of the cooperation efforts can be summarised in the following considerations, extracted by the conclusions of this report:

- The synchronisation of standardisation efforts has proven to be crucial in order to minimise fragmentation, and ensure active involvement of the end-users of the ontologies. This is fundamental in order to help standards developers using modern, cooperative tools.
- OntoCommons, with its cooperation actions, is helping to fill the gap between the understanding of the advantages brought by ontologies and their actual implementation, or usage, in applications developments. A following step will be that of involving even more leading ontology standard developers in the project, by involving them in the OntoCommons EcoSystem (OCES) validation, and promoting their participation to consultations and important project's events, such as the second Horizontal Workshop, the outputs of which will directly feed the OntoCommons Roadmap, and the final event dedicated to the OntoCommons Ecosystem.
- OntoCommons has been cited in the "Scoping study for supporting the development of a code of practice for researchers on standardisation¹", in both the 2022 and the 2021 editions. The study aims to identify elements of good practice for researchers, dealing with standards and standardisation, in the course of research projects funded by Horizon 2020. The selection of project is based on a European Commission survey sent to 2200 beneficiaries, and the application of a "must have" and bonus point criteria derived from targeted literature and expert interviews. OntoCommons, therefore, has been selected among 40 other projects as an example of good practice. This acknowledgment is an important achievement for the OntoCommons team to strengthen the project's position into the European standardisation ecosystem.

The first step towards cooperation is the definition of the community in question: for this reason, the initial activities of Task 1.2 (Specifications, Support to International Standardisation TCs & WGs & Cooperation) were dedicated to the mapping (Table 5) of EU and international **standardisation initiatives** related to the NMBP domains (Nanotechnologies, Advanced Materials, Biotechnology, and Advanced Manufacturing and Processing, with the idea to set the ground, understand the current landscape and coordinate efforts among these initiatives.

Thanks to the work carried out in collaboration with its demonstrators, the Expert Advisory Group and related projects and activities, the OntoCommons consortium has contributed to improve the harmonisation of materials and manufacturing data documentation and interoperability, including

¹ https://apre.it/wp-content/uploads/2022/03/KI0722020ENN.en_.pdf

the collection of user requirements for standardisation, which will help Standards Development Organisation understanding the industrial perspective, and therefore create more applicable and reusable standards, capable of being transposed to different domains.

OntoCommons cooperates, in fact, with 22 industrial players organised in thematic demonstrators, in order to prove the effectiveness of the OCES (Ontology Commons EcoSystem) adoption across the industrial domain. With D1.6, the team had started conducting an analysis of the standards and ontologies used, or considered for use in the future, by each of the project's demonstrators (*Table 2*), and the positive impact on their industrial processes, production, and overall competitiveness, in particular:

- Decreased development time and improved industrial systems reliability and efficiency;
- Better automation and traceability of information;
- Better representation of equipment;
- Capturing and representation of expertise;
- Routine and processes, thanks to the use of data and models to optimise production;
- Decreased time to perform certain type of operations;
- Improved communication between organisational units;
- Reduced number of hours spent on complex and repeatable work;
- Enriched data bases and easier data retrieval, reduced time thanks to the standardisation of processes and reduced manufacturing costs and environmental footprint.

In the current version of the report, this analysis has been further expanded to include information from the new set of 11 demonstrators, which were involved in OntoCommons in M16. Moreover, this second iteration has expanded the analysis outside of the project, involving the demonstrators involved in sister projects: [OpenModel](#), [OntoTrans](#), [MarketPlace](#), [VIMMP](#), [MARKET4.0](#).

What emerges from this one-of-a-kind analysis could stimulate considerations and future valuable recommendations for the standardisation domain, which will be the input of the next iteration of the OntoCommons Roadmap (D1.17, due in M36).

Compared to the first version of this document, the second part of T1.2 has moved towards organisations that are developing the standards listed in the aforementioned demonstrators' analysis, and the collaboration activities have followed this direction, in order to make the dialogue as effective as possible, and to align WP1 (Cooperation) and WP5 (Demonstration) together.

With the release of D1.6 and D1.7, OntoCommons has also achieved the project's milestone MS5 in M12 (Cooperation with standardisation Working Groups and the Technical Committees status), in that this document also monitors the progress made by the consortium in the support to, and cooperation with standardisation Working Groups and International Technical Committees. Section 4.4 of this document lists all the projects, associations and other focused CSAs that are collaborating with SDOs to bring the users' perspective, contribute to a more agile process for standardisation and provide valuable guidelines and recommendations.

Concrete actions are being undertaken to carry out the collaboration with some of these initiatives: Moreover, the project is collaborating with FAIR initiatives to integrate and test FAIR Semantics

recommendations, and with RDA and its group to elaborate recommendations for standardised data documentation based on ontologies and taxonomies. Further collaborations include the direct liaison with European and international initiatives and SDOs, and the contributions to the Metadata and Ontologies challenge of EOSC. Moreover, thanks to the liaison with StandICT.eu, OntoCommons has joined the European Observatory for ICT Standardisation (EUOS), led by the CSA H2020 project StandICT.eu, and **to support the creation of a Technical Working Group (TWG) focused on standardisation applied to ontologies**. The group of experts to join the TWG on ontologies has been identified and set-up by the StandICT.eu team. ENIT, as the technical coordinator of OntoCommons.eu, is chairing this TWG with representative Arkopaul Sarkar. The TWG is composed of diverse partners that have both ICT and industrial backgrounds. Given the versatility of the ontologies, the group has started to work on analysis that concerns both ICT and materials and manufacturing-oriented standards.

The outcome of the collaborative work carried out by the experts will be a dedicated **Landscape Report**, that will feed into the final OntoCommons Roadmap and potentially in the AIOTI Ontology Landscape report to increase the number of ontologies mapped by the expert team in this group. At the moment of writing the deliverable, the analysis is still ongoing and currently counts more than 160 standards and ontologies, including also the ones used by the OntoCommons demonstrators and other EU-funded initiatives of this field, such as [OpenModel](#), [OntoTrans](#), [MarketPlace](#), [VIMMP](#), [MARKET4.0](#), [Dome4.0](#).

Table of Contents

1. Introduction.....	10
2. State of the Art and Landscape Analysis.....	11
2.1 The relation between standards and ontologies	12
2.2 Why cooperate?.....	13
3. OntoCommons cooperation in standardisation: strategy & objectives.....	14
4. OntoCommons.eu contribution to Standards.....	16
4.1 Ontology standards and the industrial ecosystem.....	16
4.2 Inputs from the OntoCommons External Advisory Board.....	28
4.2.1 OntoCommons in the standardisation environment: an interview with Barry Smith ...	28
4.2.2 How OntoCommons will narrow the gaps between the understanding of ontologies benefits for standardisation and their implementation: an interview with Patrick Guillemin	29
4.2.3 OntoCommons and standardisation: the IOF perspective with Boonserm Kulvatunyou.	30
4.3 OntoCommons.eu & Standards: workshops' impact	31
4.3.1 Global Workshop "Ontology Commons addressing challenges of the industry 5.0 transition".....	31
4.3.2 EU-IoT and OntoCommons workshop: ontological interoperability, standardisation recommendations discussion.....	32
4.3.3 12th International Workshop on Formal Ontologies meet Industry – Session on Standardisation.....	35
4.3.4 OntoCommons at the IoT Week – Ontologies in the context of the European Green Deal.....	36
4.3.5 OntoCommons at the ETSI IoT Week.....	37
4.4 Ongoing collaborations.....	38
4.4.1 Collaborations with relevant related projects and initiatives.....	38
4.4.2 Collaborations with SDOs.....	54
5. Conclusions: Impact, Recommendations and Future Actions.....	61
6. Annex 1: Mapping of EU and international standardisation initiatives.....	64

List of Figures

Figure 1 - Interview with EAB member Barry Smith banner.....	28
Figure 2 - Interview with EAB member Patrick Guillemin banner.....	29
Figure 3 - Interview with Serm Kulvatunyou.....	30
Figure 4 - Participants type that joined the workshop.....	34
Figure 5 - Attendees' countries.....	34
Figure 6 - Role of open-source initiatives in increasing ontological interoperability.....	35

List of Tables

Table 1 - Most common cooperation actions.....	16
Table 2 - Standards applied in the OntoCommons Demonstrators.....	25
Table 3 - Standards and ontologies applied in collaborative projects.....	27
Table 3 - StandICT.eu Funded Applications in Ontologies.....	50
Table 4 - List of relevant initiatives in the NMBP standardisation area.....	71

1. Introduction

This deliverable is the second iteration of D1.6, the first OntoCommons Standardisation Impact Report. This version includes updates on the activities carried out by the project's consortium to promote the cooperation on standardisation in the industrial ontologies' community, and the description of their impact.

Compared to the previous version of this document, some sections have been restructured to provide a better framing of the activities described. The current structure of the document, although it includes – and expands – the content from D1.6, has been organised so as to answer the following questions:

1. Why is it important for the industrial ontologies community to communicate and cooperate to contribute to the standardisation of data between the materials and manufacturing domains? **Section 2** of this document answers this question by presenting the current State of the Art. In the first half of the project, OntoCommons.eu has expressed its interest in joining the StandICT2023.eu's EUOS (the EU Observatory for ICT Standardisation, an interactive platform monitoring the global ICT Standardisation landscape) in the form of a **Technical Working Group (TWG) on Ontologies** and to involve representatives from the materials and manufacturing domains. In fact, in November 2021 it was decided that ENIT, as the technical coordinator of OntoCommons.eu, will chair this TWG with his representative Arkopaul Sarkar, which will provide a **landscape and gap analysis report on Ontologies** on a global scale and provide recommendations for future work. This report will have a foreword written by an EC DG senior officer. The report being redacted at the time of the writing of this deliverable, its results cannot currently be included in this iteration. They will, however, be integrated in the document once ready.
2. What are the cooperation objectives that OntoCommons has aimed to achieve? **Section 3** presents the list of **potential actions** that the collaboration with other initiatives can offer, and their **potential impact**, as well as some **Key Performance Indicators** to measure the achievements. This has helped defining priorities and concrete timelines, as well as identifying a planning of the next steps in the remaining year of the project. This analysis has helped the project in optimising the effort towards interactions that have the higher potential impact, from those listed in the initial mapping of EU and international standardisation initiatives presented in *Table 5*, which includes a list of 38 initiatives.
3. What is OntoCommons doing in order to promote dialogue and collaboration? What is the impact of the actions carried out so far? The whole **Section 4** is dedicated to answering this question, presenting **OntoCommons' contributions** both in terms of events organised with the purpose of promoting dialogue in standardisation, and in terms of tangible interactions with the selected initiatives and participation to Technical Working Groups
4. What can still be done to further enhance the cooperation and harmonise the voice of the community? The concluding section of this document, **Section 5**, will describe what still needs to be done, as well as a **summary** of the recommendations collected so far, in order to provide a valuable input for the D1.17, second iteration of the OntoCommons Roadmap.

2.State of the Art and Landscape Analysis

On 2nd February 2022, the European Commission published a new [Standardisation Strategy](#) to ensure European leadership in global standards, boost investments in the green and digital economy, and prepare for challenges introduced by new technologies. To reach these goals, the strategy aims to shorten the European standardisation processes and improve the governance of the European standardisation system². A big part of this objective could be reached by increasing our capacity to **extract knowledge from materials and manufacturing data**, which means **adding meaning to data**, through semantics, enabling interoperability and linking up silos³.

The future of the European industry is associated with a strong modelling capacity⁴.

The field of material science relies in fact on experiments and simulation-based models to understand the “physics” of materials and discover new products that are better suitable to be used in our society, economically and environmentally. At the same time, the massive exploitation of computer-based technologies in manufacturing organisations raised the **need to manage and share data in a robust and trusted way, and harmonise different terminologies to facilitate communication**⁵. Lack of semantics and interoperability are key barriers to accessing the value hidden in raw data, whose estimated cost is about 36 billion euros⁶.

Issues related to standardization and interoperability of models, representations, and systems, are likely to emerge as more critical bottlenecks than the modelling technology itself.

Our ability to collect “big data” has greatly surpassed our capacity to analyse it⁷.

On the other hand, structured data, common knowledge frameworks and interoperability (referred to as the ability to convert, harmonise and combine distinct computer representations of material structures between two different views) have huge benefits that include higher efficiency of materials use (and consequently a reduced environmental impact), improved manufacturing value chain

² <https://www.standict.eu/eu-standardisation-strategy>

³ <https://materialsmodelling.com/data-in-materials-and-manufacturing/>

⁴ European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, *What makes a material function? let me compute the ways: modelling in H2020 LEIT-NMBP programme materials and nanotechnology projects: sixth version: short version*, Baas, A.(editor), Publications Office of the European Union, 2017, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/404734>

⁵ <https://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/hal-02537082/document>

⁶ <https://materialsmodelling.com/data-in-materials-and-manufacturing/>

⁷ <https://aip.scitation.org/doi/10.1063/1.4946894>

interactions and new business model opportunities. It is not necessary to merge knowledge bases between them, as long as separate systems are able to communicate with one another, which in turns requires standard protocols that provide interoperability between knowledge representation systems⁸.

Between a set of solutions that research and innovation can propose to overcome those barriers and achieve the ideal situation, **ontologies** are a core element because they **have the potential to integrate these resources into a computer readable concept map**, called a domain ontology, which describes concepts (entities) and relationships among the concepts in materials science and engineering⁹.

At the same time, renewed efforts to develop standards formats for engineering are taking place in various standards developing organisations, such as CEN workshops, ASTM and ISO. This work leverages existing product and testing standards with a view to engaging the engineering materials community and promote a culture of data sharing. The initial impacts of the Data Cite framework for data citation on the utilization of the European Commission materials database hosted at <https://odin.jrc.ec.europa.eu> are suggestive of a sea-change in data sharing and reuse¹⁰.

2.1 The relation between standards and ontologies

How do ontologies contribute to standards?

Standards **reflect consensus on the semantics of terms**; however, different standards might use different semantics or terms for explaining the same or very similar concepts. This is the case with standards that are used to organise data related to engineering properties and materials information, as well as ICT standards (which are fundamental in the practical applications). From one side, this aspect increases the complexity of establishing common rules that could be applied in industrial and research areas. On the other hand, this complexity can be overcome by highlighting the role played by ontologies: the work of conceptualisation, better categorisation of information and process efficiency that ontologies can offer can help establish and refine standards, for example by improving their machine-readability and thus the possibility of better and even automated implementation. It is worth noticing that the harmonisation of standards is one of the challenges identified in the European Standardisation System Roadmap¹¹.

How do standards support or inhibit shareability and reusability of ontologies?

In the workshop of Ontology Summit 2020¹² it emerged that the standards that the community needs are the ones that **enable the evaluation and comparison of ontologies**. The problem, instead, is with de facto standard that adopt ontologies without sufficient evaluation and analysis with the risk of errors.

⁸ <https://tomgruber.org/writing/AlMag12-03-004.pdf>

⁹ <https://datascience.codata.org/articles/abstract/10.2481/dsj.008-041/>

¹⁰ <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S235292451600003X?via%3Dihub>

¹¹ https://ec.europa.eu/info/law/better-regulation/have-your-say/initiatives/13099-Standardisation-strategy_en

¹² http://ontologforum.s3.amazonaws.com/OntologySummit2020/Main+Series/StandardsAndOntologies--MichaelGruninger_20200603.pdf

What makes a standard ontology?

The OntoCommons project cooperates with relevant initiatives to contribute to standardisation of ontologies, as well as to standards integration and conformance, through the use of ontologies. The standards integration concerns the **explicit representation of overlapping sets of concepts in standards**.

As concerns the standardisation of ontologies, the consensus-driven practice of the current standards development process is only the first step, the outcome of which should be **a set of semantic requirements**, that should be then validated and allow to verify the ontology.

2.2 Why cooperate?

As seen in the previous paragraphs, **Europe's competitiveness** in the domain of materials and manufacturing depends, among other factors, on its work on harmonisation and standardisation of data documentation, which in turn can increase its ability to embed digital capabilities (e.g., IoT and AI) in the operations of competitive industries and services, and it is a work that ontologies can greatly contribute to. Data standards are vital in order to increase performance while guaranteeing other crucial attributes such as FAIRness, interoperability, trust, security and reliability in data sharing. Their application in our society offers potential to ensure that data users from the manufacturing domain have access to information on what data means in the material domain (and vice versa). As a matter of fact, **data standards promote common understanding and agreement on access to information**. Putting together larger systems, of which various stand-alone systems being built today are just components, is an interesting challenge. The creation of such knowledge resources requires communitywide effort. This effort engenders a need for agreed-on conventions to enable us to build pieces that fit together¹³.

The creation of such knowledge resources requires community-wide effort.

It is, therefore, fundamental to have cooperation from the whole community, in order to build this consensus, and **to create a harmonised semantic knowledge framework open to everyone**.

Strengthening the collaboration among EU and international initiatives is fundamental, and even more important, this collaboration should also result in enhanced cooperation on standardisation: as different standards might use different semantics for similar concepts, standards alignment, integration and conformance, through the use of ontologies, can make a real difference in getting the materials domain and the manufacturing domain to communicate and be able to exchange information, setting the basis for a common ground of understanding. Without such agreement, it will remain extremely difficult to develop integrated models: harmonisation is often a mistreated

¹³ <https://tomgruber.org/writing/AIMag12-03-004.pdf>

issue that hinders the applicability of tools¹⁴, and therefore make an effort towards harmonisation and standardisation of data.

3. OntoCommons cooperation in standardisation: strategy & objectives

The role of OntoCommons is to establish common efforts to create **a framework for stakeholders working in manufacturing**, in the creation and realisation of physical products (and, therefore, in the materials domain). This framework would have the role of offering a background for these communities to get together, collaborate and create more **sustainable** products for our societies. This common background would be based on semantic models of the real world in the domains of materials and manufacturing, and the assets such as the methodologies and the ontologies used to create these models could be used and improved by this community at an international level.

*In terms of standards and standardisation, the process is long and the role, ambition and challenge of projects like OntoCommons should be to initiate standardisation processes on possible standards that are related to information modelling, information management, knowledge management.*¹⁵

With this objective in mind, the activities related to the cooperation in standardisation have been organised in the following way:

- Definition of the cooperation KPIs
- Definition of the potential actions and potential impact, according to the type of project, initiative, SDOs, SSOs, TWG or any other related institution
- Mapping of the existing standardisation initiatives at EU and international level in any of the NMBP related domains
- Actual interaction with and participation in these initiatives
- Set up of a Cooperation in Standardisation Focus Area on the website, currently joined by 254 Experts.

Initially, the team has identified the following KPIs:

1. **Mapping the standards and ontologies adopted by the OntoCommons demonstrators:** the results of this analysis are included in Section 4.1.
2. **Contribution to minimum 5 working groups that adopt ontologies and standards:** OntoCommons is currently contributing to 13 working groups; the details of these collaborations are included in Section 4.4.

¹⁴ www.sciencedirect.com | Simulation in Manufacturing: Review and Challenges; Mourtzis, D.; Doukas, M.; Bernidaki, D.

¹⁵ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ajp85Yczfh0>

- a. StandICT.eu Technical Working Group (TWG) on Ontologies (Hedi Karray, OntoCommons technical coordinator).
 - b. OAGi-IOF standardisation working group (Hedi Karray, OntoCommons technical coordinator).
 - c. INCITS 573-3-202xAd Hoc Mid-Level Ontology (MLO) standardisation working group (Hedi Karray, OntoCommons technical coordinator).
 - d. Core Terminology for Industrial Data group of ISO/TC 184/SC 4 standardisation working group (Hedi Karray, OntoCommons technical coordinator).
 - e. W3C Web of Things Working Group (Universidad Politécnica de Madrid members, part of the OntoCommons consortium).
 - f. W3C Spatial Data on the Web Working Group (Universidad Politécnica de Madrid members, part of the OntoCommons consortium).
 - g. W3C Linked Building Data Community Group (Universidad Politécnica de Madrid members, part of the OntoCommons consortium).
 - h. ETSI SmartM2M Working Group (Universidad Politécnica de Madrid members, part of the OntoCommons consortium).
 - i. Process Engineering Group of the Systems Integration Division (Boonserm Kulvatunyou, OntoCommons EAB).
 - j. IOF (Boonserm Kulvatunyou and Barry Smith, OntoCommons EAB).
 - k. AIOTI Semantic Interoperability Expert Group (Tekniker, part of the OntoCommons consortium).
 - l. EMCC Working Group on Characterisation Data and Information Management (University of Wien, University of Bologna, Goldbeck consulting, Sintef and UK Research and Innovation, part of the OntoCommons consortium).
 - m. IAOA Industry and Standards Technical Committee (Stefano Borgo, OntoCommons consortium members)
3. **Creation of one landscape analysis report, including mapping of the existing ICT, materials and manufacturing standards:** The landscape analysis is ongoing and contains 162 ontologies and standards. The report will be finalised by the end of the OntoCommons project.
 4. **Number of mapped initiatives in the standardisation arena:** we have currently collected 38 initiatives. The full mapping is included in Annex 1.

Each organisation has been approached with tangible actions, different according to the commonalities with the project. The most common actions carried out in the scope of T1.2, with some examples and impacts, are summarised in the table below.

Activity	Description	Example and impact
Joint dissemination on social media	Mentioning the initiative on social media. Creation of dedicated LinkedIn Groups or Twitter lists.	The OntoCommons demonstrators, and the OntoCommons synergies are dedicated specific promotional tweets, with dedicated graphics, on the OntoCommons social media channels, facilitating the exchange of followers and a gain in visibility.

Joint call with related initiatives	Organising joint calls, involving members of the consortium and members of related initiatives, in order to identify commonalities and paths of collaboration	Involving the initiatives in an active way, and agreeing on actions to carry out as a next step, and a follow up call to measure the achievement of such steps. One successful example comes from the collaboration with iiRDS, which ended being an OntoCommons demonstrator. The details of this activity are included in Section 4.4
Success Stories / “In Practice” Stories	Exploiting the synergies to collect their success stories coming from their use cases and providing visibility	OntoCommons can act as example for other initiatives by being featured in StandICT 2023 as a success story: https://www.standict.eu/success-stories In turn, this will also give visibility to the StandICT 2023 project thanks to the story’s promotion.
Joint event	Organising a joint event or workshop with related projects or initiatives, or inviting speakers from the synergies to an event that the project is organising.	The organisation of a joint event is fundamental to harmonise visions and speak as a common voice, and gain authoritativeness in the ontological domain, besides stimulating dialogue and increasing participation by leveraging each other’s’ networks. An example of this activity is the joint OntoCommons/EU-IoT workshop, which has reached 90 registrants and resulted in a post-event report openly accessible online .
Standardisation Activities	Involvement in project’s standardisation tasks	Contact with Technical Committee(s), Subcommittee(s) or Working Group(s) – The details of these collaborations are included in Section 4.4
Alignment	Creation and promotion of dialogue among relevant initiatives, that often work independently one from the other. Identifying common needs.	OntoCommons has made available a Focused Area, on the website, dedicated to Cooperation in Standardisation (as well as other Focus Areas for other relevant objectives of the project). The Cooperation in Standardisation Focus Area counts 254 Experts, and is being populated with relevant content available for the users.

Table 1 - Most common cooperation actions

4. OntoCommons.eu contribution to Standards

This section describes in detail all the OntoCommons contributions to cooperation in standardisation, and their impact.

4.1 Ontology standards and the industrial ecosystem

At a moment when industry is moving towards a tighter cross-domain collaboration, standardisation processes demand stronger integration of multi-domain stakeholder clusters with streamlined, digitally-supported workflows for greater efficiency.

Global information and communications technology standards create additional value and aggregate markets through technology diffusion, increased productivity, and interoperability. A more agile standards ecosystem is essential to match (and adequately serve) nowadays growing,

ever-evolving global technology environment, in order to allow both innovators and product developers to choose the best solution to fulfil their needs and to freely revise that choice in response to inevitable changes in technology and market conditions.

Industry 5.0 is driven by digital data, connectivity, and cyber systems (like Industry 4.0), but it extends these concepts adding also environmental and social factors. Industry 5.0 aims to help to frame how the industrial ecosystem and emerging societal trends and needs can co-exist¹⁶. The advent of this new business facilitates the adoption of new technologies and the increasing of data exchanged in organisations. To guarantee reliable and secure interactions between systems, a coherent approach for the semantic communication in multiple intelligent systems is vital.

In this context, the role played by standards has been heavily recognised in the industrial ecosystem as a means of improving performances and efficiency of companies' ways of working.

At the same time, ontologies support industries to improve the adoption of standards as they make them more machine readable and, as a consequence, they can be automatically implementable. Ontologies also help to connect information between different standards and represent a solution to formalise the smart manufacturing knowledge in an interoperable way.

As a matter of fact, big corporations can benefit from the adoption of ontologies because they represent the critical enablers to standardise data. This is, for example, applicable in the manufacturing area as ontologies adoption in standards facilitates the exchange of information between production plants built in different countries, which follow different rules and ways of working.

In the OntoCommons.eu context, the project team is cooperating with industrial players to develop thematic demonstrators that prove the effectiveness of adopting ontologies and standards in the industrial domain. In order to improve the interoperability in data documentation, the team has started to conduct an analysis on the ontologies and standards used to build the demonstrators. The work around standards supports the implementation of interoperability and FAIRness principles for the OntoCommons demonstrators.

The following table shows the outcome of the analysis done for the initial 11 demonstrators, already presented in D1.6, and the additional 11 demonstrators recruited in 2022.

¹⁶ https://ec.europa.eu/info/news/industry-50-towards-more-sustainable-resilient-and-human-centric-industry-2021-jan-07_en

OntoCommons Demonstrator Description	Impact	Topic and Standards/Ontologies considered
<p>1) IRIS – Industrial codesign Support (Airbus Design and Manufacturing): During the aircraft and industrial system design process, different domains engage in trade-offs and optimizations, with decisions impacting the design of other domains. A trade needs to be done between these domains, to find the most suitable design of the plant.</p>	<p>The use of ontologies and standards will enable a collaborative design process between the aircraft and industrial system domains, overcoming bottlenecks concerning knowledge management, interoperability and decision making, which will:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Help to decrease the development time, and improve the industrial system reliability and efficiency; 2. Foster a tool agnostic industrial design process; 3. Allow automation, cognitive processes and information traceability up to design choice. 	<p>Topic: Aerospace, Manufacturing</p> <p>Standards:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ISO/IEC 21838 <p>Ontologies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IOF-Core (OAGi) • QU4LITY Ontology • GRACE Ontology • Z-BRE4K Ontology
<p>2) SeDIM - Semantic Data Integration for Manufacturing (BOSCH Manufacturing): Show how the use of standardised ontologies can significantly simplify the data integration problem behind an analytical scenario at a BOSCH factory. The analytics is needed as a part of the overall goal of factory automation.</p>	<p>Knowledge Graphs, ontologies, and rules will enable the Digital Twin to correctly represent physical equipment, expertise, routines and processes with data and models to run reliable production simulation, process monitoring, analytics and optimisation.</p> <p>This will allow BOSCH to decrease the time needed to perform certain operations.</p>	<p>Topic: Manufacturing</p> <p>Ontologies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • BOSCH Ontology (In-house development)
<p>3) EngDemonstrator (Aibel Procurement): Capturing of all relevant chemical, manufacturing requirements and mechanical properties related to each manufacturing</p>	<p>The use of ontologies and ontologies will be used to enable adequate semantic definition of products to improve handover between organisational units and reduce hours spent on complex and repeatable work.</p>	<p>Topic: Process industry</p> <p>Standards:</p>

<p>grade ontology to compare material grades as listed in EN, ISO or ASTM standards</p>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ISO 15926-14 <p>Ontologies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Material-Core (In-house development) • Standards Ontology (In-house development) • ChEBI • SKOS
<p>4) Tribomat (Materials' Tribological Characterisation): This use case is collaborating with experts from top European companies in tribology, in the context of the iTribomat H2020 project: https://www.i-tribomat.eu/ to shorten the time and the number/size of experiments required to identify the behaviour of a material or combination of them (e.g. metal, coating, lubricant) with respect to specific operating conditions. The results of this demonstrator could be the first steps to pave the way towards a standard in the tribology experiments characterization, which would improve interoperability and reduce the time and resources needed for the design and execution of experiments.</p>	<p>Tekniker will use ontologies for semantic representation of tribological experiments data and model the stored knowledge in a more meaningful way to:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Reduce new material design time by 20%. 2. Reduce new material design resources by 20%. 3. Achieve a better representation of materials' experiments. 4. Enrich existing data with additional background knowledge. 5. Ease data retrieval and navigation through related resources. 6. Set the ground for developing more application-independent solutions. 	<p>Topic: Manufacturing</p> <p>Ontologies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EMMO • TribAln • VAR Ontology <p>Future Actions: OntoCommons aims to introduce the results of this use case into an SDO working on Tribological Characterisation, such as ISO (ISO 7148-1, ISO 7148-2, ISO/AWI 7148-1, ISO/AWI 7148-2, ISO 19291:2016, ISO 14830-1)</p>
<p>5) EVMF - European Virtual Marketplace Framework (Digital Materials Marketplaces): Facilitate the interoperability of platforms and services within an open European Virtual Marketplace Framework.</p>	<p>This use will use ontologies to create documentation of Materials Modelling software and describe a use case for Materials Modelling, to:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Improve VIMMP Ontologies (the semantic basis of the VIMMP platform that will facilitate exchanges between providers and users in the area of materials 	<p>Topic: Nanotechnologies, biotechnologies</p> <p>Ontologies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • VIMMP Ontologies • EMMO

	modelling) thanks to the interactions with similar NMBP platforms. 2. Provide prototypical needs from digital marketplaces.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> SWO MODA (CEN-CENELEC CWA17284)
6) PSS - Product Service Systems (OAS Product Service System): Boost logistics, production and to assure quality, in combining materials handling and weighting, in integrating weighing, dosing, mixing, logistics and control to form a unified system. This demonstrator works in close collaboration with ATB to apply the PSS ontology and provide valuable input to it, which might lead to a standard ontology for PSS (the PSS Ontology is an IOF working group ontology that intends to propose a set of standard industrial ontologies).	OAS will use ontologies to identify what modules, workflow and actors need to be considered for a new yard management service (such as devices, software, stakeholders and customer sites and infrastructure) to: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Support the standardisation of yard management services to reduce the time and effort needed for the re-configuration of the yard management system. Effectively work together with the customers and their clients to find the best definition of workflow and rules. 	Topic: Equipment industry Ontologies: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Product Service System (PSS) IOF Core Material Ontology Logistic Ontology Supply Chain Ontology
7) Feedstock Quality Assurance (Fraunhofer Quality): Measurement of different feedstocks, correlation with other feedstocks quality and correlation with the quality of produced components.	This use case will use ontologies and standards to describe the type of materials involved in the mixing process, the aspect of quality assurance while mixing and the aspects of quality for finally mixed feedstock to: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Get a Digital representation of the whole mixing process. Recognise previously unknown correlations. Decide which process (machine) parameters have to be adjusted. Achieve consistent feedstock quality. 	Topic: Quality assurance of powder blends Standards: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ISO 13320 DIN ISO 4497 BET DIN 66131 DIN ISO 3923-1 DIN ISO 3923-2 DIN 66137-1 DIN 66137-2 Ontologies: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> EMMO

8) NanoMaterials Characterisation (IRES Nano-Materials): Performance of a series of field measurements in order to characterise the airborne particle number concentration (PNC) that results from additive manufacturing activities.	IRES will use ontologies to: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Automate the experimental data collection process. 2. Achieve the semantic integration of data from different experimental measurements. 3. Study the correlation between Material Characterisation and Safety Domain through reasoning. 	Topic: Chemicals, 2D materials Ontologies: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • OYSTER Mechanical Testing Ontology • eNanoMapper Ontology • Additive Manufacturing Ontology • EMMO • BFO
9) Ontology-based Maintenance (BLM Group Ontology-based maintenance): Standardise the terminology of the maintenance process, focusing in particular on the diagnosis of technical malfunctioning, and leveraging on the knowledge extracted from service information flows and repair records.	Laboratory for Applied Ontology ISTC-CNR is using ontologies to cover terms related to the machine's parts and structure, design, functions and malfunctions to: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Reduce the costs and increase the quality of the maintenance processes. 2. Create comprehensive records of maintenance cases, frequency and solutions. 3. Perform an assessment of new anomaly cases and associated solutions. 4. Alignment of terminology across internal (and possibly external) personnel. 	Topic: Equipment industry Ontologies: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DOLCE
10) Cu/Al Data (Elvalhalcor Metal Industry): Semantic representation of technical documentation throughout Halcor's entire value chain in order to achieve data harmonization, data interoperability and interconnectivity.	ElvalHalcor is using ontologies to modify the company's data models in a way that ensures data integration and interoperability, and contribute to the development of a Smart Decision System based on raw material and production process data and specifications that will: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Optimise product quality. 2. Reduce manufacturing costs. 3. Reduce the environmental footprint. 	Topic: Manufacturing Ontologies: in-house development

<p>11) Complex Equipments (Siemens Digital Manufacturing): The main goal of the use case is to show how the use of ontologies and reasoning can significantly improve flexibility in manufacturing, as well as increase transparency and trust of AI systems by using methods for explaining AI-based decision-making. This use case will provide a data layer as part of the IOT platforms of Siemens that reduces application/ customer-specific data provisioning and integration costs. To that end, Siemens will develop an ontology library that covers various relevant domain ontologies as well as ontology transformations of various industrial standards.</p>	<p>Siemens is using ontologies to create a library of shared, reusable data models that:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. are be used as training material for developers and other stakeholders. 2. create best practice for data model governance as well as modelling tools (also for domain experts). 	<p>Topic: Manufacturing</p> <p>Standards:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ISO 15936 <p>Ontologies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • QuED • SSN • UMATI • eClass • OPC-UA (in-house transformation from the standard) • CFIHOS
<p>12) Basajaun (Paramountric): The Basajaun project aims to demonstrate how wood construction chains can be optimised to foster both rural development and urban transformation. The project is building two demo buildings and is supported by a software platform. This platform would benefit from having a connection to an ontology layer and to related tools to cater for interoperability with and between supply chain domains and actors.</p>	<p>Through the adoption of ontologies, the use case aims to:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1.achieve the state-of-the-art principles and the best possible strategy for horizontal ontology development and alignment between actors (and domains) across supply chains; 2. fit in the best possible way into European international standards 3. apply the horizontal ontology layer to the most important supply chains in manufacturing that concerns sustainability measures for saving energy, waste and climate. 	<p>Topic: Manufacturing, processing, materials development, supply-chain.</p> <p>Ontologies: ifcOWL</p>
<p>13) Chemical Product Life Cycle (BASF): The main objective of the use case is to define the life cycle of the product, from the extraction of raw materials to end of life fate and treatment (e.g., recycling, landfilling, incineration).</p>	<p>BASF will use ontologies to:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1.Facilitate, as much as possible, automatisation of calculations and sustainability assessments for chemicals; 2. Collect and analyse information about inputs and outputs associated with the life cycle of the product, such as 	<p>Topic: Chemical products manufacturing and sustainability assessment.</p> <p>Ontologies: BONSAI ontology</p>

	consumption of resources, emissions, costs, and information on social aspects; 3. Calculate, integrate and interpret sustainability impacts through indicators addressing the environmental, economic and social performance of products, including also material criticality and circularity aspects.	
14) Architecture design and ontology definition for Onboard Maintenance System of Aircraft (COMAC BATRI): Onboard Maintenance System (OMS) is one of the important systems in aircraft, it is responsible for fault diagnosis and prediction, as well as data collection and transmission. However, due to its complexity, modelling OMS is recognised as a tough task for avionics development in aircraft design.	The use case proposes the the KARMA (Kombination of ARchitecture Model specificAtion) to support architecture design and process definition of OMS with a model-based systems engineering approach. KARMA is expected to support descriptions and simulations of different architectural views of systems engineering.	Topic: Aircraft and aerospace. Ontologies: GOPPRRE Ontology
15) Automative operators' safety (CPSoSaware): This use case will develop a semantic data integration framework that will facilitate the monitoring of the human operators' safety and well-being as they are performing the requested operations. A set of IoT sensors send their measurements to respective analysis components: (a) wearables (inertial measurement units, i.e., accelerometers and gyroscopes) for motion analysis and body tracking; (b) footage from static cameras analysed by computer vision components for estimating the operator's posture.	Standardising the terminology and improving the cross-domain interoperability of CPSoSaware's will help to: 1.develop knowledge-based tools for scene analysis, posture recognition, and ergonomic assessment in a manufacturing environment; 2.have a practical deployment of FAIR-compliant semantic knowledge representation and data integration in an industrial manufacturing setting; 3.testing the deployed solutions in additional industrial scenarios proposed by OntoCommons.	Topic: Manufacturing, assembly, processing Ontologies: SSN / SOSA
16) Food Knowledge Graph (Dynaccurate): This use case will develop a proof-of-concept knowledge graph which is geared for additive or compound discovery in the sector of food processing or agri-science.	The ontology use will link databases available from the European Institutions to discover and substitute compounds to be used as additives, as well as potential usage limits etc. The main task of the use case is to keep ontologies in the knowledge graph consistent after updates and maintenance.	Topic: Biotechnology Ontologies: FoodON

<p>17) Industrial Internet of Things (iiRDS): The use case aims to learn how to model terminologies as ontology and place iiRDS in the general architectural framework.</p>	<p>Through the adoption of ontologies, the use case aims to create a productive application of the iiRDS packages prototype for EDGE devices to:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Analyse and evaluate the customer benefits of an iiRDS delivery. 2. Estimate the effort, benefits and risks of generating and maintaining the data: for technical communicators and across teams. 3. Define requirements for a roll-out. 	<p>Topic: Manufacturing, Technical Communication</p> <p>Ontologies: iiRDS Ontology</p>
<p>18) IKEA Knowledge Graph (IKEA): IKEA holds a lot of knowledge and understanding of people's lives at home, needs, wishes, dreams, and problems, as well as solutions to those. This knowledge is spread out and stored in data silos. In order to serve IKEA's digitalisation transformation efforts, the IKEA Knowledge Graph sets as its goal to connect the data and make it usable throughout IKEA's services and systems.</p>	<p>The IKEA use case benefits from the OntoCommons project's technical know-how and ontologies solutions to make IKEA's data usable throughout its systems.</p>	<p>Topic: Home Furnishing, Materials modelling.</p> <p>Ontologies: In-house development (IKEA)</p>
<p>19) Materials Databases Integration (Linköping University): The Materials Design Ontology is used for semantic and integrated access to the computational materials databases in the OPTIMADE consortium, dealing with the heterogeneity of the databases in terms of underlying data models and use of terminology.</p>	<p>This use case will investigate data integration and interoperability between top-level ontologies such as EMMO, to align MDO and EMMO/a top-level ontology as much as possible.</p>	<p>Topic: Materials development</p> <p>Ontologies: EMMO, PROV-O, CheBI, QUDT</p>
<p>20) Materials Characterisation Ontology NanoMECommons (Goldbeck Consulting): The NanoMECommons project is ontologising characterisation to capture potentially any type of</p>	<p>The use case aims to ontologise materials characterisation with human-readable metadata called CHADA and the work is to provide an EMMO compliant ontology. Moreover, the project aims to utilise OntoCommons recommendations for</p>	<p>Topic: Materials characterisation</p> <p>Ontologies: EMMO, Mechanical Testing Ontology</p>

materials characterisation method and enable harmonisation.	ontology development and implementation and ensure TLO/MLO compliance.	
21) Lubricant Designer (SCIENOMICS): SCIENOMICS is developing a platform of virtual experiments for sustainable materials and product development. These virtual experiments integrate materials and process simulation technology. The demonstration case will show how using domain ontologies it is possible to develop value-adding workflows and, on a practical level, how to develop a Designer for lubricants that fulfil both materials and use constraints.	SCIENOMICS aims to benefit from the OntoCommons project's expertise to to adopt the relevant ontologies that would allow the interoperable communication between different simulation engines which are involved in a virtual experiment.	Topic: Materials Development, Processing, Life Cycle assessment Ontologies: Materials Design Ontology
22) Solution for Soiless Culture Nutrient (UFRGS): The use case aims to Semantic representation of heterogeneous IoT devices using unified IIoT ontology, based on well-established ontologies, in order to mitigate interoperability problems in industrial applications (data interoperability and interconnectivity).	The use case is developing an industry 4.0 oriented ontology, based on the IEEE 1872 international standard, is in development to: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. automate production of a nutrient solution is of paramount importance for soiless culture applications, e.g., hydroponics agriculture techniques 2. monitor the environment and remote controlling a sequence of processes through heterogeneous IoT devices equipped with different sensors. 	Topic: Agriculture, Industry, IoT Ontologies: QU Ontology, SSU Ontology, IoT-Lite Ontology, POS Ontology, ROCO - RoboticCloud Ontology

Table 2 - Standards applied in the OntoCommons Demonstrators

In addition to this, the OntoCommons has also cooperated with EU-funded projects that are using standards and ontologies in supporting the development of their use cases. The examples below present the standards and ontologies used by the projects OntoTrans, OpenModel, MARKETPLACE, VIMMP and MARKET 4.0.

EU-funded project	Impact	Topic and Standards/Ontologies considered
1) OpenModel (Integrated Open Access Materials Modelling Innovation Platform for Europe): OpenModel aims to design, create, provide, and maintain a sustainable integrated open platform for innovation which delivers predictable, validated, and traceable simulation workflows integrating seamlessly third-party physics-based models, solvers, post-processors and databases.	OpenModel aims to bridge the gap from industry challenge via translation to actionable results that enable well informed business decisions. Six use cases (Success Stories) show the applicability to a wide range of materials and their related processing technologies and demonstrate how OpenModel facilitates setting up experiments, reducing error and enhancing development efficiency.	Topic: Materials and Manufacturing Standards: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • standard vocabularies (RDFS, SKOS, DCTERMS, DCAT) Ontologies: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EMMO used as top-level standard • Datamodel Ontology • Mapping Ontology • CIF & Crystallography Domain Ontology • Atomistic and electronic domain Ontology • Microstructure Domain Ontology • Success story-specific application ontologies (not publicly available)
2) OntoTrans (Ontology driven Open Translation Environment): the project responds to the need of industry to respond to manufacturing challenges more efficiently by accessing the relevant information and utilising materials modelling more effectively. In particular, there is a need to strengthen the use of translation as a router supporting end users to get to relevant data and models.	OntoTrans provides a general purpose ontology-based Open Translation Environment (OTE) able to support the development of dedicated Apps delivering a smart guidance for materials producers and product manufacturers (including associated Translators) through the whole steps of the translation process with the final aim to improve decision making processes in a smart integration of Open Simulation Platforms (OSP), data-driven models, materials databases, exploratory and recommendation system and ontology driven database.	Topic: Manufacturing, Artificial Intelligence Ontologies: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EMMO used as top-level standard • Datamodel Ontology • Mapping Ontology • CIF & Crystallography Domain Ontology • Atomistic and electronic domain Ontology • Microstructure Domain Ontology
3) MARKETPLACE: the project aims to leverage software engineering to	MARKETPLACE designs, creates and maintains a sustainable web-based platform that helps integrate	Topic: Materials, Manufacturing Ontologies: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EMMO

collect, adapt and integrate industrial modelling components through High-Performance-Computing resources.	components connected to the materials and manufacturing domains. In order to achieve so, the project develops standards for data, models based on cross-domain interoperability.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MAEO ontology • EVMPO ontology • OIE ontology • Production systems ontology
4) VIMMP: the main objective of VIMMP is to promote the exchange of data between materials modelling stakeholders to increase the innovation level for the European manufacturing industry.	VIMMP establishes an open-source marketplace accessible by manufacturing industrial players. The marketplace is built on taxonomy and metadata foundations, such as the ones linked to materials models, software tools, communities, translation expertise and training materials.	Topic: Materials, Manufacturing Ontologies: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MACRO ontology • MMTTO Ontology • OTRAS Ontology • VICO Ontology • VISO Ontology • VIVO Ontology • VOV Ontology
5) MARKET 4.0: the project built a multi-sided business platform to plug and produce industrial product service systems	MARKET 4.0 defines, develops and validates an open multi-sided marketplace, based on a trusted peer-to-peer data sharing infrastructure for Industry 4.0. The platform brings together Industrial Product Service Systems (IPSS) providers (supply side) and Original Equipment Manufacturers (OEMs) as their customers (demand side) facilitating the exchange of information and improvement of sales of production equipment.	Topic: Manufacturing Ontologies: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MSD11 ontology • Sensor ontology from the ICP4Life project

Table 3 - Standards and ontologies applied in collaborative projects

Moreover, other EU-funded projects (SEMANCO, Oyster, NanoCommons, DMD4F, Falcon, VIMMP, RESPOND, CoBrA, SEAS, Azure Digital Twins, DELTA, SARGON, datAcron, IoTcrawler, Fiesta-IoT, MMI, Bio2RDF, SADI, FoodON) that have built ontologies in their lifecycle, have been mapped and included in the landscape analysis report, co-prepared with the StandICT TWG on ontologies.

This preliminary analysis shows practical examples of implementing standards and ontologies in industrial systems. However, it also highlights the difficulty of adopting common standards or ontology rules in the manufacturing and materials ecosystems, issue that might be overcome thanks to the development of the OntoCommons Ontology EcoSystem (OCES). It consists of ontologies and tools following specific standardisation rules, that can be used as foundation for data documentation in the industrial domain to facilitate data sharing and valorisation and overcome the existing interoperability bottlenecks. Future recommendations on how to overcome this issue can also feed the second release of the OntoCommons Roadmap (D1.17).

4.2 Inputs from the OntoCommons External Advisory Board

The OntoCommons External Advisory Board members, and in particular those directly involved in the standardisation domain, have been involved in the cooperation efforts by collecting their recommendations through dedicated interviews, that have been published on the OntoCommons website:

4.2.1 OntoCommons in the standardisation environment: an interview with Barry Smith

Figure 1 - Interview with EAB member Barry Smith banner

Barry Smith, SUNY Distinguished Professor of Philosophy at the University of Buffalo, has emphasised the strong relation between ontologies and standards, as two sides of the same coin. In the interview he talks about the main priorities and challenges for standardisation in the ontologies domain, identifying among them the problem of managing ontologies through websites or repositories, which often results in broken links or out-of-date information. He has stressed the importance of having available resources for potential users and the benefit of this approach for the engineering and industrial communities.

Many people have found a way to understand new kinds of data thanks to the successful use of ontologies. Ontologies make data more generally understandable and usable. They do this by providing controlled vocabularies, which are used to tag data organized using often meaningless codes using terms which make the data understandable and relevant.

The full interview is available at the following link: <https://www.ontocommons.eu/news-events/news/ontocommons-standardisation-environment-interview-barry-smith>

4.2.2 How OntoCommons will narrow the gaps between the understanding of ontologies benefits for standardisation and their implementation: [an interview with Patrick Guillemin](#)

Figure 2 - Interview with EAB member Patrick Guillemin banner

Projects like OntoCommons help fill the gap to develop standards between ontology standardisation efforts and active involvement of the end-users of ontologies.

Patrick Guillemin is Technical Officer at ETSI: in his interview he has identified as a crucial priority the synchronisation of ontology standardisation efforts, in order to minimise fragmentation and ensure active involvement of the end-users of the ontologies, in order to develop standards with modern cooperative tools, like those proposed by the [ETSI SAREF portal](#).

The full interview is available at the following link: <https://www.ontocommons.eu/news-events/news/how-ontocommons-will-narrow-gaps-between-understanding-ontologies-benefits>

4.2.3 OntoCommons and standardisation: [the IOF perspective with Boonserm Kulvatunyou](#)

Figure 3 - Interview with Serm Kulvatunyou

I see in projects like OntoCommons the potential to produce technical content or expertise in the ontology standardisation and development. So, in the context of standardisation, they should become like a neutral party, that provides unbiased technical content to ensure the technical integrity of the standards and the quality of the ontology standards.

Boonserm Kulvatunyou, Ph.D., is an industrial engineer in the Process Engineering Group of the Systems Integration Division (SID) of the Engineering Laboratory at the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST).

At the moment of writing, the interview has been recorded and is in the process of being published on the website.

Boonserm Kulvatunyou has focused on the aspect of how standards and ontologies facilitate the sharing and reusing of data thanks to the increase in interoperability. He works closely with the IOF and has brought the example of the IOF experience and needs in terms of models, software and the interaction between software and hardware.

One of the priorities he has identified is to demonstrate the domain specific ontology or sub domain ontology in the industrial domain and how people can extend this for the core ontology.

The full interview is available at the following link: <https://www.ontocommons.eu/news-events/news/ontocommons-and-standardisation-iof-perspective-boonserm-kulvatunyou>

4.3 OntoCommons.eu & Standards: workshops' impact

Over the last two years, the OntoCommons.eu project has organised a series of workshops to highlight the benefits brought by ontologies and standards in industrial ecosystems. The main achievements gained by each of them are summarised below.

4.3.1 Global Workshop "Ontology Commons addressing challenges of the industry 5.0 transition"

On 2-5 November 2021, the team has organised a session entirely dedicated to Standards, in the [Global Workshop "Ontology Commons addressing challenges of the Industry 5.0 transition"](#).

The session was chaired by Silvana Muscella, CEO at Trust-IT, the partner which leads the OntoCommons Dissemination, Exploitation & Sustainability work package, as well as the specific task, in the Cooperation work package, dedicated to Specifications, Support to International Standardisation TCs & WGs & Cooperation. The workshop entitled: "Enabling intra-ontology interoperability through shared terminology" and was focused on the European and Global efforts for the cooperation on standards. It has been organised around four "Impulse Talks", of 15 minutes each, and a final panel discussion among the four panellists, with the objective to investigate on how OntoCommons.eu could build on existing solutions for ontology standardisation in the global setting, to enable intra-ontologies interoperability.

The first panel of the session concerned Ontology Standards in ISO, presented by Barry Smith, Director at the National Center for Ontological Research. Barry Smith, prominent contributor to both theoretical and applied research in ontology, outlined the current state of play with regard to the ISO/IEC 21838 standard: this standard is composed of several parts, two parts of which have already been approved and are currently in the publication stage.

The second talk, was run by Boonserm Kulvatunyou, project manager for the infrastructure for data exchange standard development and use project in the Systems Integration Division at the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST), USA, explained how it is possible to "Improve the efficiency and effectiveness of systems integration and interoperability using ontology". The talk was focused on the challenge of developing a consistent enterprise-wide data model, and on the fact that, if this model is ontology-based, it may also be more tractable thanks to the possibility of using a reasoner to assist in model consistency checking. For this reason, the Industrial Ontology Foundry (IOF) is working to provide the basic building blocks to build a consistent enterprise-wide data model.

The third speaker of this session was Ulrike Parson, current Steering Committee Chair of the iIRDS Consortium that develops and maintains a standard for the delivery of smart content. Ulrike Parson's presentation was focused on industrial standards in the internet of things, enabling interoperability and information exchange between components and services. It was focused as well on the role that ontologies play for the IoT standardisation, creating a shared understanding of and terminology for technical capabilities, product features, and service properties, as well as enabling efficient machine-to-machine and human-to-machine communication. This impulse talk was closed with an overview of the challenges that must be faced when developing industrial ontologies, such as missing reference architectures, the required level of ontology knowledge with subject matter experts and more. The last impulse talk was presented by Dr Nicolas Figay, system architect at Airbus Defence and Space at Elancourt, France, and Airbus expert in the area of interoperability for PLM, involved as <https://www.ontocommons.eu/>

an international expert in the standardization community (ISO SC4 TC184, ASD Strategic Standardization Group, liaison OSLC ISO TC184 SC4), and in research within the area of Product Data Exchange and Sharing (RISESTEP, SAVE), Interoperability of Technical Enterprise Application for Networked Collaborative Product Development (ATHENA), Model Driven Architecture/Model Driven Engineering (OpenDevFactory) or Dynamic Manufacturing Network (IMAGINE).

Airbus has been continuously working on open manufacturing data standards in order to ensure interoperability between technical enterprise applications, for supporting effective collaboration between people and organization. For such a continuous operational interoperability, both open standards and ontologies, in conjunction with Model Driven Architecture, Service Oriented Platform and Enterprise modelling, are important and connected enablers. Through the analysis of past and current experience, the presentation pointed out some important challenges to consider for implementing the roadmap about common European Ontologies.

4.3.1.1 Impact of the discussions

The inputs collected from the speakers' presentations and discussions during this session of the workshop have been included into the chapter dedicated to standardisation of the first release of the OntoCommons.eu Roadmap.

The discussions have provided significant inputs that can guide the future efforts and can be summarised as follows:

- There is a lot going on in the standardisation landscape, and one of the current challenges is that of keeping track of the ongoing efforts. OntoCommons.eu plays an important role as it can help aggregate the information and pool it together in the work related to Cooperation on Standardisation.
- The industrial domain values the endorsement from ISO, and ISO references are said to be available in open source & for public use.
- EU efforts & ESOs are working on SMART Standards, so it is useful to create a link with our initiative.
- The OntoCommons.eu Consortium is creating a connection with the EC DG GROW & DG Connect, in order to explore the possibility of setting up a dedicated chapter on Ontologies & Semantic interoperability within the 2023 edition of the ICT Rolling Plan of Standardisation.
- Dedicated efforts on developing SMART standards that are agile & market responsive need to be tackled with end-users through dedicated interoperability test-bed frameworks, and OntoCommons should have as an objective to find the right channels that can allow that.
- Even more attention should be dedicated in the future to the connection between National and International Standards Bodies.

4.3.2 EU-IoT and OntoCommons workshop: ontological interoperability, standardisation recommendations discussion

On 7 July 2022, the OntoCommons and EU-IoT projects have jointly organised a workshop focused on ontological interoperability and standardisation recommendations.

The event theme concerned semantic interoperability and, in particular, the role played by ontologies in providing interoperability. These themes are significant in the standardisation field as semantic interoperability is one of the key pillars of open and flexible IoT systems and ontologies are a key

component of semantic interoperability, as they provide the foundation and capability for machines to interpret and infer knowledge from different data sets. Ontologies are, however, often vendor or protocol based, and therefore, building universal ontologies or addressing mechanisms that can support an adequate interconnection across different ontologies is time consuming and error-prone.

To assist in overcoming the above-mentioned challenges, the online workshop was dedicated to the discussion of the status of ontological interoperability provided by different key stakeholders, and to a panel discussion for recommendations that can facilitate a better deployment of ontological interoperability across different vertical domains.

The workshop was divided into two main parts. The first one was moderated by Rute Sofia, IIoT Competence Center Head at fortiss and EU-IoT member, and aimed at presenting ontological Interoperability, challenges, and key priorities in existing EU initiatives.

The first session speaker was opened by Hedi Karray, Professor and Sr. Ontologist at the Ecole Nationale d'Ingénieurs de Tarbes and OntoCommons Technical Coordinator, who presented the OntoCommons project. His presentation was followed by Lamprini Kolovou, Project Manager at Martel and EU-IoT project coordinator, who introduced the EU-IoT project.

After them, Ray Walshe, Assistant Professor at Dublin City University and Director of the EU Observatory for ICT Standards, and Arkopaul Sarkar, Postdoctoral researcher at Ecole Nationale d'Ingénieurs de Tarbes, OntoCommons team member and Chair of the StandICT TWG on ontologies, presented the StandICT.eu project and the work carried out by the ontologies TWG in terms of landscape analysis.

Rute Sofia followed their presentation introducing the standardisation and open-source activities carried out by EU-IoT and Laura Daniele, Senior Scientist at TNO and Co-Chair of the AIOTI WG on Standardisation and Interoperability, presented the AIOTI Working Group Standardisation priorities. The last two speakers were Mauro Dragoni, Researcher Scientist at Fondazione Bruno Kessler, who explained the main objectives of the SmartM2M Working Group and their contributed to the development of ETSI SAREF; and Antonio Kung, co-founder of Trialog, who explained the OpenDEI project focus on standardisation for interoperability.

The second part was moderated by Rita Giuffrida, Researcher at Trust-IT and OntoCommons member, and was focused on gathering insights and recommendations for ontological interoperability across vertical domains. The experts invited to share their perspective on the topic were Stefano Borgo, Director of the Laboratory for Applied Ontology and member of IAOA, Boonserm Kulvatunyou, Mauro Dragoni and Laura Daniele.

The main outcomes of the workshop are summarised in the next paragraph.

4.3.2.1 Impact of the workshop

The workshop got 90 registered participants and 40 enthusiastic attendees, mainly coming from Research institutions, Academia and Industry. They were primarily joining from Europe, but the workshop proved to be interesting also for people living outside Europe, like USA or Australia as shown in the figures below.

Figure 4 - Participants type that joined the workshop

Figure 5 - Attendees' countries

The participants got the opportunity to share their perspectives through interactive sessions that aimed to understand their perspective on challenges and key priorities on ontological interoperability. In particular, one of the main outcomes from this session, was that the participants gave high relevance to the role played by open-source initiative to increase ontological interoperability.

Figure 6 - Role of open-source initiatives in increasing ontological interoperability

As mentioned, the aim of the workshop was to gather insights and recommendations from the experts invited to join the workshop. The main outcomes are summarised below:

- To prevent fragmentation, experts highlighted the need to ensure that information models are not dependent on specific protocols or vendor-based information, but the encoding of data may always exhibit some dependency which needs to be considered in open standards.
- To promote cross-domain interoperability, experts consider the use of open-source and open ontologies to be essential. However, it is also relevant to consider a universal language and a universal approach to mapping across different ontologies. The examples of IOF-core for industry and COBE for the biomedical domains have been suggested as good examples to derive further modelling; SAREF and its extensions to different domains is also a relevant starting point to achieve a global approach for cross-domain mapping.
- Open-source, open ontologies and tooling that can provide examples of application have been considered essential to achieve interoperability. Examples can promote both intra- and inter-domain harmonisation of ontologies.

The workshop has been recorded and posted online on the YouTube channels of OntoCommons and EU-IoT. Moreover, the projects have also jointly developed a post-event report with the main outcomes and recommendations [openly accessible online](#).

4.3.3 12th International Workshop on Formal Ontologies meet Industry – Session on Standardisation

The 12th International Workshop on Formal Ontologies meet Industry (FOMI22) event, was organised by the OntoCommons project to provide a platform for academic researchers and industrial practitioners to meet to analyse and discuss application issues related to methods, theories, tools, and applications based on formal ontologies in the domains of manufacturing, materials, and supply chain.

Among the various presentations, there were two sessions dedicated to standardisation:

- Upper ontology and standards for industry, with Hedi Karray (ENIT), Serm Kulvatunyou (NIST), Elisa Kendall (Thematrix Partners LLC), David Leal (Caesar system) and Michela Magas (Industry

Commons Foundation): During this session, the various speakers shared an overview of the use of ontologies in industrial standardisation activities, which started with the addition of glossaries at the beginning of each standards to drive the right interpretation and fix the meaning of the various terms used in the standard. The presentations highlighted that ontologies are changing standards in four ways: linguistic rewriting (to systematise the terminology and make the material exploitable with the new knowledge representation and reasoning tools), ontological re-organisation (to re-organise the standard to maximise conceptual clarity), ontological re-conceptualisation and ontological interoperability (to build standards that are applicable even when there are ontological disagreements). The session also provided a brief history of industrial standards with some insights on the reason behind the great number of conflicting standards, such as the fact that different committees develop data models for their domains, not looking for commonalities in other standards and the difficulty to reuse these data models. The session then ended by identifying ontologies as solution to improve the reusability of independent data models, despite their business-specific constraints.

- Upper ontology and Standards for Materials Science with Gerhard Goldbeck (Goldbeck consulting), Emanuele Ghedini (University of Bologna), Silvana Muscella (Trust-IT Services), Norman Swindells (Ferroday limited) and Alexandru Todor (Fraunhofer): During this session, the various speakers shared the requirements for a materials ontology at the upper level, such as meaningful conceptualisation of matter and material and representation of their characteristics. The presentation introduced the ontological challenge to organise data in a way that unites all the sub-communities within materials science and the need to recognise this plurality of perspectives, since each of these domains has its own language and ways of handling data. For example, the taxonomies within the various materials science domains should inherit their fundamental meaning from the upper-level ontology, which should also deal appropriately with existing cross-domain concepts from different standards. This session ended by highlighting that materials science standards identify engineering properties and that different standards give a specific property different meaning according to the perspectives and processes used for its measurement within the specific standard, such as the different definitions of molecule from a chemistry and physics perspective. Therefore, since a property and its meaning are related to the process of its measurement within a specific standard, the materials science upper ontology has the critical role to harmonise the different semantics from the various standards related to the same property.

4.3.4 OntoCommons at the IoT Week – Ontologies in the context of the European Green Deal

The IoT Week is an annual event where experts in industry and academia share their insights on the role played by Internet of Things (IoT) technologies in the digital transformation. In 2022 the event took place in Dublin from 20 to 23 June and Raúl Garcia Castro, from Universidad Politécnica de Madrid and OntoCommons partner, was invited to join the workshop “Ontologies in the context of the European Green Deal” organised by the Semantic Interoperability Expert Group of the AIOTI WG Standardisation. The session was chaired by Laura Daniele, Co-Chair of the AIOTI WG.

The event was divided into 3 main parts:

- the 1st part revolved around an introductory session where Martin Bauer, Co-Chair of the AIOTI Semantic Interoperability Expert Group, presented the activities performed by the AIOTI WG on semantic interoperability to develop the Ontology Landscape; and Svetoslav Mihaylov, Policy Officer at the European Commission, introduced the EU perspective on the Twin Green and Digital Transition;
- in the 2nd part, the speakers had the opportunity to discuss how to develop and use ontologies for the European Green Deal, the usability of ontologies and requirements from industry, and relations to other initiatives. The speakers of this session were:
 - Raúl García-Castro, that presented examples on how to enable semantic interoperability in the European Green Deal;
 - Gjalt Loots, Researcher at TNO, who explained how to use ontologies on a large scale to InterConnect Smart Homes, Buildings and Grids;
 - Dave Raggett, W3C team member, that showed the usability and scalability of Knowledge Graphs;
 - Enrico Scarrone, manager at Telecom Italia, who provided an overview of the role played by ontologies and standards in industry;
 - Alberto Abella, Technical Evangelist at FIWARE, who provided examples of agile standardisation with the Smart Data Models Program;
 - Aitor Corchero, Semantic Web architect at Eurecat, who showed examples of how to adopt data spaces inside the water sector.
- the final part introduced a panel discussion with all the speakers based on their statements and questions from the audience.

The main recommendations from the workshop are summarised below:

- European projects play a key role in deploying ontology-based solutions for interoperability at high maturity level and on a large scale. OntoCommons is a good example as the project aims to build the OntoCommons Ontology EcoSystem to overcome interoperability issues in the materials and manufacturing fields.
- The value of adopting semantics and ontologies is well understood by both research and industry, but the latter find them still too challenging to implement.
- Lack of tools and trainings represent an issue that needs to be overcome to share knowledge and increase the adoption of ontologies in industry.
- The usability of large knowledge graphs and ontologies needs to be improved to increase their adoption.
- The standardisation process is often perceived as taking too long by industrial partners and there is still a lack of understanding of how we can standardise new ontologies. An example is provided by SAREF in ETSI.

4.3.5 OntoCommons at the ETSI IoT Week

The ETSI IoT Week 2022 has taken physically place in ETSI premises, Sophia Antipolis, France, on 10-14 October 2022. The ETSI IoT Week consisted of a series of events: a tutorial on ontologies and semantic interoperability for IoT on 10 October, and the ETSI IoT Conference on 11-14 October with demonstrations on 11-13 October.

Following the organisation of the joint workshop between EU-IoT and OntoCommons, the projects were invited to give a speech about the main outcomes of the online event. Arkopaul Sarkar, Researcher at ENIT and one of the speakers of the EU-IoT OntoCommons workshop in July, presented the session entitled “EU-IoT and Ontocommons Workshop Ontological Interoperability and Standardization: Recommendations and Application of Ontologies in Cross-Domain” at the ETSI IoT Week, on 11 October, to highlight the work performed by the two projects in terms of ontological interoperability and the main outcomes of the joint workshop.

4.4 Ongoing collaborations

Given the CSA-nature of OntoCommons, the project aims to build a community of relevant stakeholders to share the results of the project and strengthen the efforts towards ontology-driven standardisation activities across materials and manufacturing domains.

Since the launch of the project, OntoCommons started a continuous engagement with relevant initiatives in the standardisation ecosystem. An inventory of initiatives has been continuously updated and now includes more than **38 potential contacts**. From these contacts, Ontocommons.eu has begun a specific collaboration with a number of these that is elaborated in the sections below. The following paragraphs show practical details of some of the initiatives OntoCommons is collaborating with in the standardisation area, contributing to the definition of user requirements that standards need for the materials and modelling community to be able to exploit them. A complete list of all the initiatives can be found in the WP1 Deliverables “Cooperation Monitor”, current version 3, D1.3 was submitted in M18.

4.4.1 Collaborations with relevant related projects and initiatives

4.4.1.1 AIOTI

About

The Alliance for IoT and Edge Computing Innovation (AIOTI) aims to lead, promote, bridge and collaborate in IoT and Edge Computing and other converging technologies research and innovation, standardisation and ecosystem building, providing IoT and Edge Computing deployment for European businesses creating benefits for the European society.

The two projects share the common objective of facilitating the adoption of ontologies for successfully implementing semantic systems and achieving semantic interoperability between the systems in various domains.

Standards

Just like OntoCommons, with their standardisation activities AIOTI aims to be recognised as a major contributor to the semantic interoperability of manufacturing and materials-related domains, in particular IoT and edge computing.

OntoCommons can therefore build upon and reuse AIOTI’s results and vice versa to allow both projects to drive forward their standardisation activities in a synergic way.

Type of collaboration

OntoCommons and AIOTI have carried out and are exploring various cooperation activities.

Iker Esnaola from Tekniker, part of the OntoCommons consortium, is also member of the AIOTI Semantic Interoperability Expert Group that, in December 2021, has published the [AIOTI Ontology landscape report](#) (of which Iker is an editor) to help researcher in choosing the ontologies that could be suitable candidates in a given use case for the successful implementation of semantic systems and for achieving semantic interoperability between the systems.

Related to this report, on Wednesday 29 June 2022, various members of the OntoCommons community have joined the "[AIOTI WG Standardisation Ontology Landscape Report Presentation webinar](#)" that presented the current version of the AIOTI ontology landscape, engaged in open discussion with interested stakeholders and planned the next steps on how to evolve the Ontology Landscape.

Deeper ties between OntoCommons and AIOTI were created on Thursday 7 July 2022, during the "[EU-IoT and OntoCommons workshop: ontological interoperability, standardisation recommendations discussion](#)" joint workshop, where Laura Daniele, AIOTI co-lead of the Semantic Interoperability Task Force of the AIOTI Standardisation WG, joined the event with two sessions:

- Session I: Perspectives on Ontological Interoperability, challenges and key priorities - AIOTI WG priorities, where Laura introduced the AIOTI semantic interoperability group goals, past activities and current activities and events, among which the AIOTI ontology landscape report. The session also provided a detailed overview of the report and how the IoT ontologies included were classified.
- Panel discussion: Recommendations for ontological interoperability across vertical domains - AIOTI WG priorities: During the panel, Laura shared the importance of having ontologies that harmonise the information of the various standards within a specific domain

Impact

OntoCommons is planning to build upon the results of the AIOTI Ontology landscape report by including the ontologies summarised in the document into the "OntoCommons and StandICT.eu TWG ontologies landscape report" to create a more comprehensive analysis.

Next steps:

Given the synergic nature of the ontologies landscape analysis of both documents, OntoCommons is planning to share the outcomes of the upcoming OntoCommons and StandICT.eu TWG ontologies landscape report in the next iteration of the AIOTI ontology landscape document.

4.4.1.2 CAESAR Systems

About

CAESAR Systems is a company regularly working with SDOs and standardisation-relevant organisations or projects to provide consultancy in engineering data management and standards.

Type of collaboration

David Leal, founder of CAESAR system, is an HSBooster expert reviewer, a member of the OntoCommons community and among the expert members of the OntoCommons Standardisation Focus Area.

David supported the activities of the OntoCommons demonstrators by providing his feedback on the standards and ontologies used by the OntoCommons demonstrators, in particular on any missing standard that could be adopted by them to achieve the goal of their use cases.

David Leal also joined the [12th International Workshop on Formal Ontologies meet Industry \(FOMI22\)](#) as speaker in the Upper ontology and standards for industry sessions:

- 13 September 2022, Upper ontology and standards for industry - Terminologies and ontologies as a basis for industrial data standards.
- 13 September 2022, Upper ontology and standards for industry - Panel discussion.

In these sessions, David provided a brief history of industrial standards and an overview of industry reference data libraries and dictionaries. David also provided some insights on the reason behind the great amount of conflicting industrial standards, saying that different standards committees develop data models for their domains, not looking for commonalities in other standards and that reusing fragments of existing data models is difficult.

Standards

CAESAR Systems is involved in the development and implementation of the following International Standards:

- ISO 10303-209: Composite and metallic structural analysis and related design.
- ISO 10303-221: Functional data for process plants and their schematic representation.
- ISO 15926-2: Lifecycle data for process plants - Data model.
- ISO/TS 15926-3: Lifecycle data for process plants - Reference data for geometry and topology.
- ISO/TS 15926-4: Lifecycle data for process plants - Initial reference data.
- ISO/CD-TS 15927-6: Lifecycle data for process plants - Methodology for the development and validation of reference data.

Impact

David Leal is supporting the work of OntoCommons, by sharing with the project's community his valuable expertise, such as harmonisation of upper and domain ontologies, domain ontologies used as reference data for existing standards, domain knowledge extracted from existing standards and expressed as ontologies, etc.

Next steps:

OntoCommons is liaising with David Leal to explore future collaborations, such as event participation in the OntoCommons 2023 global workshop, the possible participation of David Leal in the OntoCommons and StandICT.eu TWG or relevant activities in the OntoCommons Standardisation Focus Area.

4.4.1.3 Industrial Ontologies Foundry (IOF)

About

The IOF (<https://www.industrialontologies.org/>) is an industry driven community that aims to co-create a set of open reference ontologies to support the manufacturing and engineering industry needs and advance data interoperability. IOF aims to work with Government, Industry, Academic and Standards organizations to advance data interoperability in their respective fields. IOF has joined OAGi (<https://oagi.org/>) as a formal legal entity.

Type of collaboration

Members of the OntoCommons EAB are members of the Governance Board of the Industrial Ontologies Foundry - IOF (Barry Smith, Boonserm Kulvatunyou) and the same Dimitris Kiritsis, member of the OntoCommons consortium and WP1 leader, is also member of the IOF Governance Board and one of the Technical Oversight Board co-chairs.

OntoCommons and the Industrial Ontologies Foundry have co-organised five sessions during the recent 12th International Workshop on Formal Ontologies meet Industry (FOMI22) event:

- The Industrial Ontologies Foundry (IOF) – Monday 12 September, 11:30 – 12:00 CEST.
- IOF Systems Engineering – Wednesday 14 September, 10:30 – 12:30 CEST.
- IOF Maintenance Reference ontology – Wednesday 14 September, 10:30 – 12:30 CEST.
- IOF/Mat-o-Lab Toolchain – Wednesday 14 September, 14:00 – 15:45 CEST.
- IOF Governance and Architecture – Wednesday 14 September, 17:45 – 18:15 CEST.

Thanks to multiple connections between OntoCommons project partners (ENIT, UiO, ATB) and IOF OntoCommons is regarded as a member of this community, contributing to the development of the creation of a standardised set of open industrial ontologies that spans the entire domain of traditional manufacturing, in collaboration also with OAGi (Open Application Group). Common terms used for the IOF Core ontology are Failure event, Maintenance notification, Maintenance notification trigger, Maintenance schedule list, Maintenance task, Product, Process, Infrastructure, Resource and Software. Recently, IOF released the first version of its IOF Core Middle Level Ontology that has been used in the AIRBUS demonstrator. Furthermore, a number of IOF Working Groups are developing Domain Ontologies in domains such as Supply Chain, Maintenance, Product Service Systems, Production Planning and Scheduling, ZDM (Zero Defects Manufacturing) etc., that could be implemented by some of the OntoCommons demonstrators. The IOF Supply Chain ontology is expected to be released soon.

Standards

The standards shown below represent the ones developed by the Industrial Ontologies Foundry, that the OntoCommons project can benefit from over the course of the project:

- ISO/IEC 21838-1:2021 Information technology — Top-level ontologies (TLO)
- ISO/IEC 21838-2 Information technology — Top-level ontologies (TLO)
- BFO - Basic Formal Ontology

Moreover, the IOF Core ontology, a middle-level ontology developed by IOF is ready to be officially released. OAGi, the hosting organisation of IOF, will establish an IOF membership category, accept ownership of ontology artifacts developed by the IOF, and release them under MIT and CC BY 4.0 (or similar) licenses. The IOF adopted BFO as the TLO to support the development of the IOF Core ontology.

Impact

The first version of the IOF Core ontology has been released. The demonstrator “Airbus design and manufacturing” on co-design support uses IOF Core to support the development of the corresponding application ontology.

The Industrial Ontologies Foundry and OAGi will produce open Industrial Ontologies that span the entire domain of digital manufacturing. The OntoCommons members involved in the IOF are contributing to this work. An IOF Supply Chain Domain Ontology is expected to be released soon.

Next steps:

Currently, there are eight Working Groups under IOF covering a variety of industrial topics of interest such as Maintenance, Production Planning and Scheduling, Supply Chains, Product Service Systems, Manufacturing Equipment Connectivity (MTConnect), Systems Engineering and Zero-Defect Manufacturing, which are expected to publish their respective Domain Ontology modules in the next period.

4.4.1.4 EMMC ASBL and EMCC

About

The [European Materials Modelling Council \(EMMC\)](#) is an initiative started informally in 2014, supported by a H2020 CSA project 2016-2019 and founded as a not-for-profit association EMMC ASBL in Brussels in 2019. The main remit of EMMC is to support, coordinate and represent the field of materials modelling and digitalisation for industrial application and impact. From the start, EMMC has been working on establishing a common language that helps to bring together the various domains and sub-disciplines and achieve a standardised documentation (referred to as MODA). This work culminated in a CEN Workshop Agreement CWA 17284 (more information is provided in the following sections) which formed the basis for the development of an ontology that can support materials science and applied sciences in general. The result is the EMMO, formerly European Materials Modelling Ontology, now called Elementary Multiperspective Material Ontology, which provides a general ontological framework consisting of Top and Middle Level Ontologies. EMMC is the governing body for EMMC TLO and MLO developments.

In addition, the [European Materials Characterisation Council \(EMCC\)](#) is an informal association supporting similar aims in the materials characterisation field. Following the example of the EMMC

work on standardised documentation of materials modelling (MODA), the EMCC community elaborated a documentation terminology and template (CHADA) for characterisation.

Type of collaboration

The collaboration between OntoCommons and EMMC as well as EMCC is facilitated in particular via OntoCommons partners TU Wien (Nadja Adamovic is EMMC President), GCL (Gerhard Goldbeck I EMMC Executive Secretary and member of the EMCC management board) as well as UNIBO, SINTEF, UKRI and Tekniker, which enables a close interaction.

EMMC collaboration with OntoCommons is crucial due to EMMC (together with EMCC) being the leading European stakeholder association representing the materials digitalisation field, with a strong basis in ontologies. The cornerstone, as mentioned above, is the EMMO ontology, which is one of the three TLOs of the OCES. UNIBO, GCL and SINTEF are co-authors of EMMO and UNIBO leads WP2 of OntoCommons on the TRO.

Via EMMC, EMCC and related projects there is a strong collaboration with a wider stakeholder network involving many related Horizon projects. These are managed in EMMC via the [Focus Area Interoperability and Digitalisation](#), with active Task Groups covering different materials domain ontologies. In addition, EMCC has a Working Group on Characterisation Data and Information Management including MODA & CHADA work and collaboration with EMMC.

Furthermore, in the leading European initiatives in the Materials field, the [Advanced Materials 2030 Initiative](#) (see also section on EUMAT), Gerhard Goldbeck (on behalf of EMMC) leads the Working Group on Materials Digitalisation, currently finalising the respective part of the AMI2030 Roadmap.

Standards

EMMC and EMCC have elaborated and are applying CEN Workshop Agreements for the terminology, classification and documentation of materials modelling and characterisation, respectively. These CWAs have been carried out with support from related H2020 projects (MODENA and EMMC-CSA for CWA 17284 and OYSTER for CWA 17815).

- CWA 17284: Materials modelling - Terminology, classification and metadata¹⁷
- CWA 17815: Materials characterisation - Terminology, classification and metadata¹⁸

Both these standards and the semiotic approach taken by EMMO to the declaration of properties are well aligned with the information model of ISO 10303-235 (AP235) which basically states that any property definition requires the processes by which a property value is determined.

The role of standardised data documentation is also strongly highlighted in the AMI2030 Roadmap.

¹⁷ https://www.cencenelec.eu/media/CEN-CENELEC/CWAs/RI/cwa17284_2018.pdf

¹⁸ <https://www.cencenelec.eu/media/CEN-CENELEC/CWAs/ICT/cwa17815.pdf>
<https://www.ontocommons.eu/>

Impact

The CWA standards have been and are being used as a basis for EMMO ontology implementations that underpin materials modelling marketplaces and open innovation environments in characterisation. Currently, under EMMC auspices, there is a Task Group on a Materials Characterisation Methodology Domain ontology that is based on CWA 17815.

OCES recommendations are very much sought and starting to be applied in these projects (such as NanoMECommons) for example regarding ontology engineering (competency questions etc) and ontology maintenance, as well as regarding integration of and alignment with other existing ontologies.

Further impact will be achieved by OntoCommons bringing together the materials communities represented in EMMC/EMCC with the product and related standards efforts in ISO/TC 184/SC 4 and future updates to ISO 10303 (see ISO section).

Overcoming current barriers to materials data (re-)use via a common terminology, taxonomy and ontologies and the application of the OntoCommons OCES are key topics in the AMI2030 roadmap and forthcoming Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda. EMMC and OntoCommons are working closely on this agenda.

Next Steps:

The collaboration between OntoCommons and EMMC ASBL and EMCC will revolve the following points:

- Establishing a set of materials domain ontologies that can serve as a standard for data documentation in the materials field.
- Providing input to the AMI2030 roadmapping and SRIA process via AMI2030 WG1 on Materials Digitalisation led by EMMC.
- Liaising between EMMC/EMCC/EMMO communities and ISO/TC 184/SC 4.
- Working with EMMO regarding compliance with ISO standards for TLO.

4.4.1.1 EUMAT

About

The European Technology Platform for Advanced Engineering Materials and Technologies [EUMAT](#) aims to assure optimal involvement of industry and other important stakeholders in the process of establishing of R&D priorities in the area of advanced engineering materials and technologies. EuMaT should improve coherence in existing and forthcoming EU projects, in the field of materials R&D. EuMaT covers all elements of the life cycle of an industrial product, regardless if it is a component, a system or a final good. EuMaT is a European Technology Platform (ETP) established as public-private partnership at European level. EUMAT engages a wide network across different sector value chains, in particular through the Alliance for Materials (A4M), a joint initiative of technology platforms, academia, research institutes, and industry, working in the field of materials. EUMAT is working with the Materials for Energy initiative (EMIRI), the Manufacturer Platform and SUSCHEM (the Sustainable chemical initiative) as well as EMMC and EMCC.

<https://www.ontocommons.eu/>

 company/ontocommons

Type of collaboration

OntoCommons Partner Tekniker is the co-secretary of the EUMAT Platform and a core partner in the Advanced Materials [AMI 2030 initiative](#). Tekniker coordinated the writing of the first draft of the [Materials 2030 RoadMap](#).

Also, Tekniker is working in the Safe and Sustainable by design concept, where both modelling and characterisation, and their digitalisation, have an important role in the prediction at the laboratory of the component's behaviour in real practice. This knowledge can be linked with the monitoring of the behaviour of the components in real components.

During the "Reinventing materials research, towards accelerated development by closely orchestrating AI, data, robotics and high performance computing" event, the OntoCommons [poster "Characterising tribological experiments through semantic technologies"](#) was presented at the EMIRI stand.

Standards

EUMAT in general and the AMI2030 initiative in particular highlight the importance of an enabling policy framework through harmonised criteria for safe and sustainable by design chemicals and materials, evidence-based life-cycle assessments, harmonised norms and standards, robust health and safety protocols as well as targeted education and training actions across the value chains.

Standardised data documentation via ontologies is highlighted as a key part of the enabling technologies for materials digitalisation in the AMI2030 roadmap.

Impact

OntoCommons OCES plays an important role in the AMI2030 roadmap. See also the section on EMMC.

Next Steps:

The collaboration between OntoCommons and EUMAT will further revolve around the role of OntoCommons OCES in the AMI2030 initiative.

4.4.1.2 EU-IoT

About

EU-IoT acts as an accelerator for the whole European IoT ecosystem towards transforming the current IoT community of researchers and innovators in Europe into an increasingly cohesive, dynamic, participatory and sustainable ecosystem, as an essential part of the [Next Generation Internet](#) initiative. It assists stakeholders to engage and create value, as well as set up a self-sustaining European IoT community.

The two projects share the common objective of facilitating the use of ontologies by the research community to increase semantic interoperability in different vertical domains, such as Internet of Things, manufacturing and materials.

As Coordination and Support Actions (CSA), EU-IoT and OntoCommons can support SDOs in their standardisation activities by providing recommendations and identifying challenges needed to address and to foster interoperability.

Type of collaboration

OntoCommons and EU-IoT have organised the joint event "[EU-IoT and OntoCommons workshop: ontological interoperability, standardisation recommendations discussion](#)" to discuss the current status of ontological interoperability and collect recommendations provided by different key stakeholders that can facilitate a better deployment of ontological interoperability across different vertical domains.

The event had 90 registered participants in Eventbrite and an average of 40 active participants during the actual event.

The participants represented experts in ontology-related fields who mainly work in universities, research institutions, industries, and SMEs. They were primarily joining from Europe, but the workshop proved to be interesting also for people living outside Europe, like USA or Australia.

Standards

OntoCommons has joined forces with EU-IoT to engage with their community and collect their feedback on the semantic interoperability key priorities and challenges addressed by different SDOs, such as AIOTI, NIST, etc., on the interoperability recommendations that should be addressed in OntoCommons and on suggestions for the coordination of standardisation efforts.

Impact

On Tuesday 11th October 2022 at 16:30 CEST, OntoCommons and EU-IoT joined the session 4 "Adoption and Usability of Ontologies and SAREF" of the [ETSI IoT Conference](#) (part of the [ETSI IoT week 2022](#)) with the joint session "EU-IoT and Ontocommons Workshop Ontological Interoperability and Standardisation: Recommendations and Application of Ontologies in Cross-Domain".

During the session, the projects presented the "[EU-IoT and OntoCommons workshop: ontological interoperability, standardisation recommendations discussion](#)" [post-event report](#), which included the highlights from the various sessions of the "EU-IoT and OntoCommons workshop: ontological interoperability, standardisation recommendations discussion" event, including the results of the interaction sessions. The report highlighted that the participants currently use standards and ontologies in manufacturing, ICT, energy, healthcare, and

IT, but they face several challenges in applying standards and ontologies to their field of expertise, such as fragmentation of information models (related to vendor lock-in), expressivity and incompatibility of upper ontologies, or incompatibility of versions.

Most participants indicated that they perceive open-source initiatives as being crucial to increase ontological interoperability.

While some attendees believe that it is crucial to use existing standards and extend them to other domains whenever possible (32%), the majority (68%) feels the need to create new standards in

specific sectors, like AI, Digital Twins, Circular Economy, Secure Trusted Chips, Life Cycle Management, and Digital Product Passport.

Next steps:

OntoCommons and EU-IoT are liaising to explore and agree on additional activities for their future cooperation.

4.4.1.3 IAOA

About

The [International Association for Ontology and its Applications](#) (IAOA) is a non-profit organization promoting interdisciplinary research and international collaboration at the intersection of philosophical ontology, linguistics, logic, cognitive science, and computer science, as well as in the applications of ontological analysis to conceptual modelling, knowledge engineering, knowledge management, information-systems development, library and information science, scientific research, and semantic technologies in general. The Association was formally established in Trento (Italy) in 2009 and relocated in Bern (Switzerland) in 2013. The association concentrates on spreading the knowledge, adoption and use of ontology, ontological principles and methodologies in all areas and domains and has been pivotal in introducing modern modelling views. This is done primarily via public events including the [Formal Ontology in Information System](#) conference series and the Formal Ontology in Industry workshop series, as well as by supporting students, young researchers and other personnel via scholarships to attend ontology-related conferences and meetings. IAOA also establishes liaisons with other organisations with similar goals to create synergies and foster the scientific use of ontology.

Type of collaboration

OntoCommons has established collaborations with IAOA in several ways including:

- Participation of IAOA members as partners in OntoCommons.
- Participation of IAOA representatives in OntoCommons workshops across 2021 and 2022.
- Invitation of a keynote speech of the IAOA President Laure Vieu at the OntoCommons Global Workshop in November 2021.
- Co-organization of the FOMI 2021 workshop in September 2021 and September 2022.
- Discussion with co-chairs of the IAOA Industry and Standards Technical Committee for the organization of events in the coming years.
- Bilateral meetings between the OntoCommons and IAOA Industry and Standards Technical Committee (IAOA-ISTC) members.

The active IAOA members involved in OntoCommons.eu are Nicola Guarino, Stefano Borgo, Claudio Masolo, Roberta Ferrario and Emilio Sanfilippo, who are involved in the Top Reference Ontology, Industrial Domain Ontologies, Ontology Commons Ecosystem Toolkit and Demonstrators WPs in OntoCommons.eu.

In particular, Stefano Borgo and Nicola Guarino are members of the Advisory Board of the International Association on Ontology and its Applications, where in the past they served in the

Executive Council. Nicola Guarino was president of the association in the period 2009 - 2013 and is currently a fellow of the IAOA. Emilio Sanfilippo, instead, is currently a member of the IAOA Executive Council.

Standards

The IAOA Industry and Standards Technical Committee (ISTC), co-chaired by Stefano Borgo, is devoted to fostering the use of applied ontology in standardization initiatives, and to facilitate the interactions across people in industry and in applied ontology research. Activities include the dissemination of information about initiatives with the aim to gather experts interested in the development of ontologically sound standards, and the organization of virtual and physical meetings and events where to discuss how to understand and apply ontological approaches and methodologies. Members of the ISTC have been active in several standardisation initiatives like:

- [ISO 18629-1:2004](#) Industrial automation systems and integration — Process specification language.
- [ISO/IEC 21838-1:2021](#) Information technology — Top-level ontologies (TLO).
- [Distributed Ontology, Model, and Specification Language](#) (OGM). [IEEE 1872.2-2021](#) - IEEE Approved Draft Standard for Autonomous Robotics (AuR) Ontology.

IAOA and OntoCommons share the view that ontology initiatives should be open to different viewpoints and aim to include the approaches taken by the several communities of experts. The development of standards based on these ideas is further fostering the use of open frameworks like OCES.

Next Steps:

OntoCommons.eu. partners are already involved in IAOA's technical committee group on standards and industry. As a parallel activity the OntoCommons.eu team has invited IAOA members to be part of the Technical Working Group on Ontologies within the remit of the StandICT.eu TWGs.

The collaboration between IAOA and OntoCommons is strong and will continue along the lines described above especially in terms of:

- Event organisations.
- Dissemination of shared results across the ontology community.

4.4.1.4 StandICT.eu

About

StandICT.eu 2023, Supporting European Experts Presence in International Standardisation Activities in ICT, GA No. 951972, is an EU-funded, Coordination and Support Action StandICT.eu 2023

addressing the specific challenges of the topic ICT-45-2020, "Reinforcing European presence in international ICT standardisation, running from September 2020 to August 2023.

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 company/ontocommons

Building on the success of the StandICT.eu 2018-2020 precursor Project, StandICT.eu 2023 has a dual objective. The first, **to support the participation of European ICT experts in international SDO Working Groups, through a series of 10 Open Calls, which will provide a total of 3 million Euro of funding** over the duration of the Project through the StandICT.eu 2023 Fellowship Programme, The second, to deliver the **“EUOS – The European Observatory for ICT Standardisation”, an interactive platform that will monitor the global ICT Standardisation landscape**, with the ultimate goal of providing the community of ICT experts with accurate coverage of relevant and timely ICT Standards into which the results of the fellowships feed and contribute.

Within the EUOS, StandICT.eu has also launched a **series of rotating Technical Working Groups (TWG) to harness expert advice and stimulate discussion among SDOs, public bodies, academic institutions and acclaimed specialists** to provide and expert overview of documents and activities relevant to standardisation in identified key fields such as Artificial Intelligence, Big Data Spaces, Blockchain, Cybersecurity, Data Interoperability, Smart Cities and Trusted Information with a **further dedicated TWG on Ontologies launched** in March 2022. Chaired by the OntoCommons.eu project, the output of this group is providing an overview of the diverse array of global standardisation work underway in Ontologies and the various organisations behind it. This information will be updated and evolve via the above mentioned EUOS database and ultimately result in the release of a dedicated Gaps Analysis Report.

The benefits of the collaboration forged between Ontocommons.eu and StandICT.eu 2023 is therefore not only easily discernible but symbiotic with obvious advantages to be gained by both on multiple facets, as outlined below:

- **Within the ontologies TWG, OntoCommons.eu** has created an ontology landscape analysis as part of its objective to **drive standardisation of data documentation** and provide **key insights on pertinent gaps, recommendations and priorities in ICT Standardisation around ontologies** for StandICT.eu’s future Open Calls.
- As a natural consequence of the above, **OntoCommons.eu may publicise the opportunities offered to its stakeholders by the StandICT.eu Open Calls** and encourage applications from individuals to apply for funding be included in the Working Groups (WG) or Technical Committees (TC) of the SDOs working on standardisation around ontologies and **concrete examples of where this type of cooperation has yielded results** over the first 12 months of the project in terms of funded experts working on ICT and industrial standardisation activities in ontologies are provided below.
- **OntoCommons.eu may also take part in webinars and events organised by StandICT.eu 2023 and vice versa**, or contribute to the Standards Assembly foreseen upon conclusion of StandICT.eu. Likewise, **each may bring its use cases to be showcased at events as practical results of the projects** and in the StandICT.eu 2023 EUOS.

Funded Applicants in Ontologies from the StandICT.eu Open Calls

A list of the successful applications received in response to StandICT.eu Open Call #3 and #4 to fund activities on ontologies applied to standards (and vice versa), at the time of writing is provided in the table below.

Title	EU Priority	SDO
IoT Semantic Interoperability - Specialization to Energy and relationship to AI	Key Enablers and Security	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ISO SC41 IoT and Digital Twins • ISO SC42 AI
Participation in SA WG4 and Contributions to Augmented Reality in 3GPP Mobile AR Report TR26.998	Key Enablers and Security	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IEEE RAS Standards Working Group - Ontologies for Robotics and Automation
Ontologies' Standardisation and Harmonization for Industry Commons (SHICO)	Sustainable Growth	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • OAGi (Open Applications Group)
Development of content delivery standard for smart content, iiRDS	Sustainable Growth	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • iiRDS
iiRDS, Working Group participation and Maintenance Domain extension	Sustainable Growth	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • iiRDS
QuaFair: Data quality assessment through Contextual Intelligence using the FAIR data methodology	Key Enablers and Security	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IEEE ComSoc Internet of Things Emerging Technical Subcommittee
Open Ethics Transparency Protocol RFC	Innovation for the societal challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ANEC
Building Information Modeling, WG4 – Support Data Dictionary	Key Enablers and Security	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CEN
Improving the adoption of BIM according to ISO 19650 in the construction sector in the Netherlands	Sustainable Growth	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ISO
Semantics and concepts to enable interoperable conversions between calendar systems	Sustainable Growth	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ISO
Danish participation in the ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 32 WG 3 Database languages (SQL and new GQL), 3rd term	Key Enablers and Security	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ISO/IEC

Table 4 - StandICT.eu Funded Applications in Ontologies

Among these applications some of them are strictly related to the OntoCommons.eu project and have already reached a state of maturity to gather the first results and impacts:

- Hedi Karray, professor at ENIT and OntoCommons technical coordinator, has submitted the application called “Ontologies' Standardisation and Harmonization for Industry Commons (SHICO)”: this project is highly aligned with the aims and objectives of the 2021-2022 work program of Horizon Europe related to the digitalisation of the European industry, in which data sharing and interoperability in a heterogeneous environment are major challenges. Ontologies are presented as a valuable solution for interoperability and semantic data sharing. However, for various reasons, ontologies are often not themselves interoperable and thus fail to be widely accepted. Establishing a shared semantic basis, open and standardized ontologies contributions, and the co-innovation abilities as well as via fostering translation, SHICO will provide a boost to Open Digital Innovation.

The work led by Hedi Karray contributes to the work of three standardisation groups: **OAGi-IOF**, **INCITS 573-3-202x Ad Hoc Mid-Level Ontology (MLO)** and **Core Terminology for Industrial Data group of ISO/TC 184/SC 4**.

Within the OAGi-IOF group, Hedi Karray will participate in the group IOF-core to contribute to the elaboration and the review of IOF core Ontology through the following activities:

- New Term Introduction & Term Evolution (Development & Test)
- Formalisation of the IOF-Core Relationship (for the extensive use of Common Core Ontology terms within IOF Core term definitions)
- Representation of N-ary relations in OWL
- Modularisation of IOF Core
- Mid-level terms (classes & relations): mid-level modules
- Relations: industrial relations module.

Within the INCITS 573-3-202xAd Hoc Mid-Level Ontology (MLO), Hedi Karray will participate in the elaboration and the review of Information technology – Mid-Level Ontology (MLO). His involvement will include the participation in the following activities:

- Contribution to the definition of the scope of middle-level Ontology
- Contribution to generalise and “de-militarise” the Common Core ontologies by working on definite classes, the annotation of classes by adding general examples, and by working on the relations ontology.

Within the activities of the Core Terminology for Industrial Data group of ISO/TC 184/SC 4, he will contribute to the elaboration, the review, and the ontological alignment of the Core Terminology for Industrial Data. His involvement will include the participation in the following activities:

- Contribution to the identification and definition of terms
- Contribution to align terms with Basic Formal Ontology (BFO).

Webinars and events organised by OntoCommons.eu with participation of StandICT.eu

The OntoCommons.eu team has organised two webinars in which Silvana Muscella, OntoCommons.eu standardisation task leader and StandICT.eu project coordinator, has joined and presented the potential collaborations between the two projects. During the first webinar "[OntoCommons.eu: An industrial ontology journey exploring the benefits of Standardisation, FAIR Data & Innovation](#)", organised on 23 February 2021, the attendees had the opportunity to learn more about how OntoCommons.eu can liaise with StandICT.eu to create a Technical Working Group for experts collaboration and consultation on ontologies and standards. The second event, organised on 30 September 2021, "[What can ontologies do for standardisation? OntoCommons.eu project in the standardisation ecosystem](#)" added additional content on the open calls funded by StandICT.eu 2023 that supports work to align existing ontologies and ultimately contribute to filling the gap in ontology-based Standards to support European Policy objectives. The details of the two webinars are available in D1.6.

Next Steps: At the time of writing this deliverable, exchanges have gone on with the chairs of the ICT rolling Plan of Standardisation and the Ontocommons.eu partners have been given the opportunity to add content to the new dedicated chapter entitled "Data Economy" ready for the ICT Rolling Pan 2023 edition. The Technical Working Group on Ontologies, building upon its ontology landscape analysis, will start working on a gap analysis report focused on standardisation applied to ontologies on a global level to provide the community of experts with the most accurate coverage of relevant and timely Standards, priorities and needs that might affect key domains of the Digital Single Market and the EU ICT Rolling Plan for Standardisation. The outcome of this report will feed into the final OntoCommons Roadmap.

4.4.1.5 RDA

About

With over 12,000 members from 146 countries, the Research Data Alliance (RDA) builds the social and technical bridges to enable the open sharing and re-use of data by addressing challenges related to data sharing, data management plans, certification of data repositories and interdisciplinary interoperability.

It was launched as a community-driven initiative in 2013 by the European Commission, the United States Government's National Science Foundation, the National Institute of Standards and Technology and the Australian Government's Department of Innovation to allow researchers and innovators to share and re-use data across technologies, disciplines, and countries to address the grand challenges of society through its 49 recommendations (specific tools, code, best practices and standards produced by its 36 working groups), which include 8 ICT technical specification.

RDA Members come together through self-formed, volunteer and focused Working Groups, exploratory Interest Groups and communities of practices to exchange knowledge, share discoveries, discuss barriers and potential solutions, define policies and harmonise standards to enhance and facilitate global data sharing & re-use.

RDA members collaborate together across the globe to tackle numerous infrastructures & data sharing challenges related to: data sharing, data management plans, certification of data repositories and interdisciplinary interoperability.

Type of collaboration

RDA proposes to provide support to identify and get in contact with the relevant stakeholders with the RDA galaxy of Interest Groups and Working Groups and provide advice to handle and sustain multi-stakeholder collaboration as developed by Task 1.3 and 1.4 in the project. This multi-stakeholder collaboration, called the Knowledge Exchange Space (KExS), already involves Interest Groups interested in ontologies such as the RDA Chemistry IG and the Vocabulary and Semantic Service IG. RDA will also help the project to identify the relevant recommendations for the OntoCommons project and its stakeholders.

Standards

RDA provides 34 recommendations on different aspects of data sharing, management and governance. Although not standards per se, they should be used as a source of information for building standards that integrate such consensus-based recommendations and technical solutions.

Impact

RDA will provide OntoCommons with existing community recommendations to be integrated and tested within the context of the project. This will accelerate the internal development of FAIR data, FAIR semantic artefacts. RDA is also a large network of experts that could be leveraged to address some of the challenges of the industrial partners.

Next Steps: Further dialog will be established with the RDA secretariat to ease the identification of the right recommendations and the right expert groups. A continuous dialog is maintained with the relevant Interest Groups identified by T1.3. and T1.4, including the Chemistry, Materials and Engineering and Vocabulary Services IGd. Through the KExS, we will invite other Interest Groups to present their work as well as Working Groups generating relevant recommendations. For the RDA 20th Plenary, Gothenburg, Sweden, March 21-23, 2023, a proposal for a Birds-of-a-feather session on Materials Domain ontologies harmonisation has been made by GCL, in collaboration and supported by the Materials and Chemistry IGs.

4.4.1.6 Dome4.0

About

Digital Open Marketplace Ecosystem 4.0 ([DOME 4.0](#)) is an RIA project, funded by the European Commission under the call H2020-NMBP-TO-IND-2020-twostage that intends to offer an intelligent semantic industrial data ecosystem for knowledge creation across the entire materials to manufacturing value chains. The ecosystem provides a sustainable solution to the information silos problem related to the past efforts and puts forward a formal, ontology-based documentation for open and confidential data spaces applicable to future and current projects thereby delivering added value. Furthermore, the flexibility of the proposed semantic architecture of DOME 4.0 naturally adapts

to the emerging Industry Commons developments and the scale-up of the ecosystem to large amounts of data, tools and services applicable to wider sectors of the European economy.

Type of Collaboration

OntoCommons has established collaborations with DOME 4.0 in several ways including:

- Participation of DOME 4.0 members in OntoCommons workshops.
- Preparation of an overview of ontologies to share with OntoCommons.
- Monthly meetings to keep up with the ontologies landscape analysis alignments from both projects.
- The “Bosch manufacturing” OntoCommons demonstrator (DOME 4.0 is the beneficiary).
- DOME 4.0 is actively contributing to the OntoCommons task 1.5 regarding marketplace alignment.
-

The expected collaborations between OntoCommons and DOME 4.0 are:

- Feedback on DOME 4.0 ontologies.
- Transfer of documents/ontologies and expertise between the projects.
- Alignment on the landscape analysis of ontologies in both projects.
- Coordinating DOME 4.0 as a marketplace via the OntoCommons task 1.5.

Standards

Key to DOME 4.0 success is in widely agreed standards for ontology-based data documentation to be further developed and recommended by the OntoCommons.eu project, as discussed in this document.

Impact

DOME 4.0 can be regarded as the **impact testbed** for OntoCommons, enabling a step change in data valorisation both within value chains and in complex cross sector utilisation of data.

Next Steps: Additional dialogues will be established to foster the cooperation between the two projects. As a matter of fact, discussions will be carried out to understand how the OntoCommons.eu ecosystem of ontologies and evaluation framework can be applied to DOME4.0 ontologies, in the context of Industry Commons Marketplaces.

4.4.2 Collaborations with SDOs

4.4.2.1 ETSI

About

ETSI supports the timely development, ratification and testing of globally applicable standards for ICT-enabled systems, applications and services, with 900+ member organizations drawn from over 60 countries and five continents.

Type of collaboration

The Consortium Partner Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (UPM) collaborates with ETSI for the SAREF (Smart Applications REference Ontology) developments as well as the SAREF development methodology. UPM has also been involved in the definition and development of the SAREF ontologies portal and is also involved in W3C Web of Things Working Group, the Spatial Data on the Web Working Group and the Linked Building Data Community Group.

Patrick Guillemin, member of the OntoCommons EAB, is technical officer at ETSI.

Standards

ETSI is defining the standard SAREF ontology and its extensions as well as establishing the methodology for developing and standardising them. In addition, one of the SAREF extensions, SAREF4INMA, focuses on the industry and manufacturing domain.

The SAREF core ontology and SAREF4INMA as well as other extensions are ideal candidates to be included in the OntoCommons ontology ecosystem.

The Universidad Politécnica de Madrid has taken part in the creation of SAREF and several extensions. In particular, their work has been focused on:

- Publication of SAREF v2 and v3
- Among the ETSI SmartM2M Technical Body has supported the production of standards
 - ETSI STF 513 (Maintenance & Evolution of SAREF Reference Ontology): SAREF4ENVI and SAREF4BLDG
 - ETSI STF 534 (SAREF extensions): SAREF4CITY, SAREF4INMA and SAREF4AGRI
 - ETSI STF 556 (Consolidation of SAREF and its community of industrial users, based on the experience of the EUREKA ITEA - 12004 SEAS project): SAREF consolidation and SAREF portal requirements
 - ETSI/EC STF 566 (SAREF extensions for Automotive, eHealth/Ageing-well, Wearables and Water): SAREF4WEAR and SAREF4WATR
 - ETSI STF 578
 - ETSI STF 602 (SAREF: Industry adoption facilitation and oneM2M ontology alignment): SAREF4LIFT

Impact

The collaboration between OntoCommons and ETSI will benefit the adoption, use and refinement of existing ontologies developed by ETSI as for example the SAREF ontology or its extensions for industry and manufacturing (SAREF4INMA) or for building devices (SAREF4BLDG). As a consequence, the communities will benefit from avoiding the duplication of efforts, building again similar models, and from adopting common standards (e.g., specific SAREF models or the underlying standards as OWL, RDFS or SHACL). In addition, common and best practices for building and managing ontologies will be shared by sharing experiences about the methodological framework for developing ontologies adopted by SAREF and OntoCommons, both based on the LOT methodology (<https://lot.linkeddata.es/>).

Next Steps: One of the future expectations for the collaboration between OntoCommons and ETSI would involve the analysis and alignment of SAREF extensions with other standard or existing models, for example for the building domain.

4.4.2.2 CEN CENELEC

About

CEN, the European Committee for Standardization, is an association that brings together the National Standardization Bodies of 34 European countries. CEN is one of three European Standardization Organizations (together with CENELEC and ETSI)

that have been officially recognised by the European Union and by the European Free Trade Association (EFTA) as being responsible for developing and defining voluntary standards at European level. CEN provides a platform for the development of European Standards and other technical documents in relation to various kinds of products, materials, services and processes.

Type of collaboration

OntoCommons.eu members from Universitetet i Oslo take part in the CEN-CENELEC Workshop Agreement (CWA) on Zero Defects Manufacturing (ZDM) in digital manufacturing terminology. The CWA defines and collates terms for zero defects manufacturing in digital manufacturing with correlation to Industry 4.0 and quality management. Indeed, the main objectives of the ZDM standardisation activity are to establish the terminology and definition of concepts associated with digital manufacturing in the context of Industry 4.0, and to explain how these concepts relate to quality management initiatives.

Industry 4.0 technologies such as smart sensors, cyber-physical systems and machine learning offer cost efficient solutions for continuous monitoring and computation that can be applied for the prediction and avoidance of manufacturing defects, leveraging the ZDM solutions blossom as a specific movement part of quality management initiative where mathematical models, IoT and robotics cooperate to prevent defects and provide a competitive edge to manufacturing companies.

The ZDM cooperates also with IOF (as shown in the section 6.2 of this deliverable) and the connection between these two Technical Working Groups can enhance and improve the ZDM ontology development.

Standards

BFO and IOF core ontologies will be used for the development of the ZDM ontology. Common terms that can be used in this process are:

- Failure event
- Maintenance notification
- Maintenance notification trigger
- Maintenance schedule list

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- Maintenance task
- Product
- Process
- Infrastructure
- Resource
- Software

Next Steps: the ZDM ontology could be used for further developing the standardisation work on selected OntoCommons demonstrators, which will be identified over the next months.

4.4.2.3 International Organisation for Standardisation (ISO)

About

ISO is a non-governmental, independent, global organisation composed of a network of the world's leading standardisers. Through their members (the national standards bodies in 165 different countries) they bring together experts from all over the world to develop International Standards. ISO ensures that the developed standards follow quality, safety, and efficiency of products, services, and systems.

International
Organization for
Standardization

Type of collaboration

Hedi Karray, OntoCommons Technical Coordinator, is collaborating within the ISO/TC 184/SC4.

This subcommittee 4 'Industrial Data' develops technology and standards for the digital representation of all engineering product data, where 'product' in fact includes materials, hence there is a very close alignment with the domains of interest of OntoCommons. The history and current work of the committee has recently been reviewed with a particular focus on materials and related information models, in particular the ISO 10303 standard and its Application Protocols are of key importance. The review highlights the opportunity for further updates to the standard that integrates materials and products into a common scheme across the life cycle. Furthermore, implementations of the related information model exist currently mostly in EXPRESS language and there is an opportunity to update to owl/rdf.

The OntoCommons.eu team is also involved in the development of other ISO standards, namely: The ISO/IEC 21838 standard is about domain-neutral top-level ontologies (TLO). The Part 1 and Part 2 of this standard are already in the publication phase. The Part 1 (ISO/IEC 21838-1, www.iso.org/standard/71954.html) specifies required characteristics of a top-level ontology that can be used in tandem with domain ontologies at lower levels to support data exchange, retrieval, discovery, integration and analysis. The Part 2 (ISO/IEC 21838-2, www.iso.org/standard/74572.html) specifies Basic Formal Ontology (BFO) as a TLO conforming to the requirements defined in Part 1. The Parts 3 and 4 in future will specify DOLCE and TUPPER as TLOs in a similar manner.

Impact

Next Steps: The team is going to attend dedicated meetings to continue contributing on the work about ISO/TC/184/SC4, and ISO/IEC 21838 standard (BFO), IOF-Core (OAGi) currently being adopted in the demonstrator IRIS-Industrial co-design Support.

4.4.2.4 iiRDS

About

iiRDS aims to establish standards that cover the request and the delivery of intelligent information between companies, organisations and individuals. The standards open new methods of advanced technical communication and iiRDS enables the delivery of precise information in the area of smart manufacturing. iiRDS has developed a Consortium that aims to advance the development of the standards.

Type of collaboration

OntoCommons and iiRDS have started cooperative discussions in the following areas:

- the standards and ontologies developed by iiRDS can be exploited for the development of a new OntoCommons demonstrator;
- the iiRDS ontology can be harmonised and made interoperable with the other ontologies involved in the OntoCommons project (e.g., EMMO, DOLCE, BFO).
- iiRDS will provide insights and recommendations to shape the OntoCommons Roadmap.

Moreover, the current Steering Committee Chair at iiRDS, Ulrike Parson, has joined panel discussions about the role played by standards and ontologies during the webinar [“What can ontologies do for standardisation? OntoCommons.eu project in the standardisation ecosystem”](#), and the session “Enabling intra ontology interoperability through shared terminology”, as part of the [first Horizontal Workshop](#), organised by the OntoCommons team. All the recommendations shared will be addressed for the preparation of the first version of the OntoCommons Roadmap.

As a results of the [call to become the new OntoCommons Demonstrators](#), iiRDS has joined OntoCommons as the demonstrator [“Industrial Internet of Things - Using iiRDS in the industrial internet of things \(IIoT\) with Siemens Industrial Edge”](#), with the aim of learning how to model terminologies as ontology and place iiRDS in the general architectural framework to create a productive application of the iiRDS packages prototype for EDGE devices:

- Using standardised vocabulary for enriching technical documentation content with metadata.
- Enabling semantic search and search facets in content delivery portal.
- Enabling targeted access and retrieval of content on Edge devices or from the Edge cloud based on use cases.

Standards

iiRDS is a standard for the delivery of intelligent information, provided with the product for the purpose of assisting the users in setting up, operating, and maintaining the product. iiRDS consists of:

- A vocabulary for the metadata provided with the content (e.g., product lifecycle phases, information types)
- A package format for the exchange of packages with intelligent information between different systems

Impact

The iiRDS Consortium representatives applied to the StandICT.eu open calls and have been successful in the third open call, in order to align iiRDS with European ontology standards and frameworks, among which OntoCommons. The goals of this alignment are:

- Adapting iiRDS in a way that it can be used with other European industry ontologies. This would enable to connect smart content as defined by iiRDS with other subject areas, i.e. sensor technology, manufacturing data, or maintenance information.
- Using common and state-of-the-art implementation methods, e.g., OWL and an architecture of upper-level, domain, and application ontology.
- Avoiding duplication of data structures that are defined by other European standardization initiatives
- Creating linked data on a European scale by providing an open standard that companies and standardisation bodies can use for delivery of smart content
- Coordinating with European and global activities regarding smart digital standards, for example driven by DKE and ISO
- Feedback the experiences from the development of iiRDS to other standardization initiatives, especially in the field of ontologies

Next Steps: as iiRDS addresses metadata and exchangeability of technical information, it may also serve to drive the digitization of standards themselves and enable dynamic content delivery for standard specifications and targeted access to requirements and definitions contained in international standard documents. This work can be useful for further driving standardisation efforts to the OntoCommons demonstrators and can define the basis for developing a new demonstrator.

Moreover, the iiRDS aims to align with the OntoCommons working group linked to Domain Ontologies and to define all the needed requirements for aligning iiRDS with the OntoCommons architecture of upper-level ontology, domain ontology and application ontology.

4.4.2.5 IEEE

About

With an active portfolio of nearly 1,300 standards and projects under development, IEEE is a leading developer of industry standards in a broad range of technologies that drive the functionality, capabilities, and interoperability of a wide range of products and services, transforming how people live, work, and communicate.

Type of collaboration

Michela Magas, OntoCommons Innovation and Sustainability Manager, has had several rounds of discussions with IEEE stakeholders on the topic of the establishment of an Industry Commons Interest Group within IEEE:

- Early interest was shown by the IEEE Industry Engagement group and by Sri Chandrasekaran, Senior Director, Standards & Technology, IEEE India, and IEEE Senior Member, IoT & Foundational Technologies Practice Lead.
- An expression of interest has been obtained from Hermann Brand, European Standards Affairs Director of IEEE to become member of the OntoCommons External Advisory Board.
- A mutually beneficial alignment is envisaged between several IEEE standardisation efforts and Industry Commons initiatives.

Standards

An IEEE standard upper-level ontology was created in 2001 by Adam Pease and Ian Niles (<https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/knowledge-engineering-review/article/abs/ieee-standard-upper-ontology-a-progress-report/215797ACBB7DACEE2C4100D18F51A04F>). In recent years IEEE has been less involved with upper ontologies but very strong on the lower layers of communication systems, including cooperation with ETSI in oneM2M to enhance 3GPP IoT network services

(<https://portal.etsi.org/Services/Centre-for-Testing-Interoperability/Activities/M2M/oneM2M>).

In the field of domain ontologies, IEEE prioritises ontologies in the AI and IoT domains, and focuses particularly on robotics and automation. In 2015 the IEEE standard for ontologies for robotics and automation was approved (<https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/7084073>). Recent ontology developments in the robotics and automation domain include IEEE 1872.2-2021 – the IEEE Approved Draft Standard for Autonomous Robotics (AuR) Ontology (https://standards.ieee.org/standard/1872_2-2021.html) and IEEE 7007-2021 – the IEEE Ontological Standard for Ethically Driven Robotics and Automation Systems.

A new standard P2957 for a Reference Architecture for Big Data Governance and Metadata Management has been proposed in September 2020 (<https://standards.ieee.org/project/2957.html>). The standard defines a big data governance, metadata management and machine-readable reference architecture to enable scalability, findability, accessibility, interoperability and reusability of datasets among corporate heterogeneous and cross-domain repositories. The expected date of submission of draft to the IEEE SA for Initial Standards Association Ballot is November 2023 and the

projected completion date for submission is June 2024. Both OntoCommons and the Industry Commons use cases can make a substantial contribution to this standard.

Impact

The collaboration between IEEE and the Industry Commons initiatives and particularly the OntoCommons project can impact on the alignment between the IEEE Reference Architecture for Big Data Governance and Metadata Management standard and the Industry Commons demonstrator use cases and ontology ecosystem building. Existing IEEE domain ontology applications in robotics and automation can provide a demonstrator use case for Industry Commons initiatives and ensure further cross-domain alignment and harmonisation.

Next Steps: An approval of Hermann Brand, European Standards Affairs Director of IEEE as Member of the OntoCommons External Advisory Board is pending by the OntoCommons Coordinator and the Executive Board at the First Year Project Review. This will be followed by a proposal for cooperation and collaborative work on the establishment of a long-term engagement and alignment with Industry Commons initiatives.

5. Conclusions: Impact, Recommendations and Future Actions

The OntoCommons Standardisation Impact Report has shown how cooperation with relevant SDOs and other standardisation stakeholders is crucial to facilitate the development and adoption of ontologies by industrial players.

This deliverable, an update from D1.6, has highlighted the critical and complementary role played by ontologies and standards in the industrial ecosystem and the aim of OntoCommons.eu to further contribute to the adoption of industrial ontologies in the standardisation field with continuous engagement with standardisation players.

This section reports the conclusions of this document and some actions to further enhance the cooperation in the remaining year of the project, and harmonise the vision of the community.

The results of this deliverable will be integrated with the outputs of the demonstrators workshop in November 2022, and of the landscape analysis, which will be released at project's end.

1. **Recommendations, gaps and priorities** around the Ontology domain from a standardisation perspective will also be listed in the **OntoCommons.eu Roadmap**. A complete list of recommendations will be provided in **the second OntoCommons Standardisation Impact Report**, due in M24.
2. The **OntoCommons OCES** can represent an important vehicle to overcome existing bottlenecks to apply standards and ontologies in the industrial sector as it supports the collection of industry-relevant data and including them in a single repository and ensuring that they are used in a consistent way.
3. The analysis brought forward by the **OntoCommons demonstrators** can influence standards from industry input and how they may become valid use cases as part of EOSC to include in

- the **EOSC Set up Task Forces**. This work will be proposed from M24, after the development and initial validation of cases have been finalised.
4. A constant monitoring of the **number of applications in the ontology domain** that are potentially supported as part of the StandICT.eu project (11 applications as shown in Table 2) and 12 active **community members** within the **Working Group of EUOS of StandICT.eu**.
 5. Finalisation and publication of the StandICT TWG landscape report to showcase the current ontologies and standards applied in materials and manufacturing domains. Some of the outcomes of the StandICT landscape analysis on ontologies can be added to the next iteration of the AIOTI Ontology Landscape report to enrich and update its content.
 6. Continuous engagement with the standardisation community: 76 people, from the **active community of members** registered on the OntoCommons.eu website, participated in the events organised and specifically related to standardisation, (the Webinar: “What can ontologies do for standardisation? OntoCommons.eu project in the standardisation ecosystem” and the dedicated session of the “Global Workshop: Ontology Commons addressing challenges of the industry 5.0 transition”, called “Enabling intra-ontology Interoperability through shared terminology”). Moreover, the Standardisation Focus Area launched in October 2022 on the OntoCommons website counts 115 subscribed members.
 7. The release of the EU’s strategy on standardisation includes the establishment of a Standardisation Booster a platform to help beneficiaries, whose Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe research results are likely to lead to the revision or creation of a standard, to test the relevance of their results for standardisation. The HSbooster.eu project will deliver a pilot of the booster. The project started in April 2022 and will run for 24 months. HSbooster.eu will provide a tailor-made online platform and resources for standardisation experts in Europe to advise 1,000 Horizon Europe and H2020 projects on how best their research results can lead to the revision or creation of standards. Services and training modules will help projects assess the standardisation readiness of their results and match them up with experts in the field who can guide them on how these results can feed into standardisation working groups or technical committees. With the Booster an integral part of the EU Strategy on Standardisation, OntoCommons will explore avenues to engage with the Booster. This could include:
 - a. Participation by individuals within the project with experience in the standardisation landscape to apply as experts and deliver support services to projects interested in discovering how their results can contribute to standardisation.
 - b. Sharing of relevant standards-related training material that could be relevant to ontology-related standards activities.
 8. Ontologies can support the reusability of manufacturing and materials data models.
 9. Materials and manufacturing scientists need to look at existing standards and extract the data from them to be expressed as ontologies (ontological re-organisation). This will simplify the models and foster data and knowledge reusability and thus, prevent all the time and money invested in the creation of these standards from going to waste for not being used because of lack of interoperability.
 10. A key challenge to address is that since terminologies and reference data are free, to foster materials and manufacturing standards and data documentation interoperability, the ontologies used to develop them need to follow the FAIR principles and, in particular, to be free and openly accessible by other researchers.

11. Standards and ontologies have the potential to facilitate the reusing of data, by increasing its interoperability, it is therefore fundamental to strengthen the collaboration among EU and international standardisation initiatives in this domain. Projects like OntoCommons should become a sort of neutral party, providing unbiased technical content to ensure the technical integrity of the standards and the quality of the ontology standards.
12. It is crucial to synchronise ontology standardisation efforts to minimise fragmentation and ensure active involvement of the end-users of the ontologies, also in order to help standards development thanks to the use of modern cooperative tools and fill the considerable gap between the understanding of the advantages brought by ontologies and their actual implementation.
13. Continuous analysis of the ontologies and standards used by the OntoCommons demonstrators. This preliminary analysis shows practical examples of implementing standards and ontologies in industrial systems. However, it also highlights the difficulty of adopting common standards or ontology rules in the manufacturing and materials ecosystems, issue that might be overcome thanks to the development of the OntoCommons Ontology EcoSystem (OCES). It consists of ontologies and tools following specific standardisation rules, that can be used as foundation for data documentation in the industrial domain to facilitate data sharing and valorisation and overcome the existing interoperability bottlenecks. Future recommendations on how to overcome this issue can also feed the second release of the OntoCommons Roadmap (D1.17).

OntoCommons.eu, through these concerted efforts, of showing how Ontologies can support standardisation, we would like to be in a position, by the project end, to demonstrate some relevant results through the diverse collaborations and results from the demonstrators and where we can prove some impacts in contributing to better efficiency, automation, information traceability, representation, optimised processes thanks to the use of data and models, ultimately through the use of Standards.

6. Annex 1: Mapping of EU and international standardisation initiatives

The table below lists the relevant EU and international initiatives currently mapped, related to ontology-based standardisation of data documentation in NMBP domains. The mapping is a continuous activity which is still in progress.

Number	Organisations related to Standards efforts	Type of collaboration
1	AIOTI – Alliance for Internet and Edge Computing Innovation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TEKNIKER and UPM are members of the AIOTI. • Patrick Guillemin, OntoCommons EAB member is head of the standardisation WG for AIOTI and can engage with AIOTI on the project’s behalf. • The TEKNIKER team has contributed to the 1st release of the Ontology Landscape in Dec 2021 via his membership in the AIOTI Semantic Interoperability Expert Group. • Some of the outcomes from the StandICT landscape analysis on ontologies could be added to the next iteration of the AIOTI Ontology Landscape report. This can be facilitated by the fact that members of the AIOTI WG have joined also the StandICT ontologies TWG.
2	BDVA - Big Data Value Association/DAIRO	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TEKNIKER and ATB (part of the OntoCommons consortium) are members. • OntoCommons will liaise with BDVA to utilise their outputs.
3	CEN - European Committee for Standardization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dimitris Kiritsis (WP1 leader) participated in a meeting on a new standard on Zero Defect Manufacturing (ZDM) organized by DIN/CEN/CENELEC. The participants have the intention to work with ontologies in this domain and the idea is to create a WG on ZDM in IOF.
4	CFPC - Carbon Fibres & Advanced High-Performance Cluster	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TEKNIKER (part of the OntoCommons consortium) has contacts with this working group through the EUMAT Platform. • OntoCommons will liaise with CFPC to utilise their outputs.
5	CO-LaN	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Michel Pons attended the OntoCommons Doric Kick-off event on 15th March 2021.

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • OntoCommons will liaise with CO-LaN to utilise their outputs
6	DDI - Data Documentation Initiative	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Joachim Wackerow attended the TLO/MLO workshop in March/April 2021. • OntoCommons will liaise with DDI to utilise their outputs
7	ECLASS or eCl@ss-Standard for Master Data and Semantics for Digitalization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First contact initiated • Collaboration scope not defined yet
8	EMMC - The European Materials Modelling Council	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is a close connection with OntoCommons via individuals and organisations participating in both. • EMMC has disseminated OntoCommons events. • OntoCommons and CNR (part of the OntoCommons consortium) joined the EMMC International Workshop, March 2021. • EMMC will join OntoCommons' s Focus Areas on "Interoperability" and "Digitalisation". • The Ontology EMMO (governed by EMMC) is used by various OntoCommons demonstrators.
9	EOSC - European Open Science Cloud	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • OntoCommons identified three relevant EOSC Task Forces to either establish close working relationships on technical and semantic interoperability of data and FAIR metrics. • There is a close connection with OntoCommons via individuals and organisations participating in both. • Members of EOSC joined the OntoCommons Event: "Creating a Knowledge Exchange Space for data management and documentation – KexS". OntoCommons joined the EOSC Symposium with a session on the Alignment and harmonisation between EU marketplaces and synergies and collaboration opportunities between EOSC and OntoCommons.
10	ETSI (including developments of SAREF - Smart Applications REFerence Ontology, and extensions)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mauro Dragoni, Research Scientist at Fondazione Bruno Kessler is one of the main developers of SAREF contributed in several standards-based events organised by the OntoCommons team. • Patrick Guillemin, Technical Officer SmartM2M, CABLE, eHealth, ISG CIM and IoT/Smart Cities Coordinator, former AIOTI WG03 IoT Standardisation Chairman, AIOTI

		<p>Steering Board Member, is member of the OntoCommons External Advisory Board.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • OntoCommons liaises with ETSI SAREF to analyse their outputs. • UPM (OntoCommons consortium) has developed several SAREF extensions and the SAREF latest versions. • OntoCommons will liaise with SAREF to utilise their outputs.
11	EUDAT Collaborative Data Infrastructure (EUDAT CDI)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First contact initiated • Collaboration scope not defined yet
12	European Multi Stakeholder Platform on ICT Standardisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Ontocommons consortium aims to contribute content to the new chapter "Data Economy" within the ICT Standardisation rolling plan 2023
13	IAOA - International Association for Ontology and its Applications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is a close connection with OntoCommons via individuals and organisations participating in both. • Members of IAOA attended the OntoCommons Doric Kick-off on 15th March 2021. • Members of IAOA attended the TLO/MLO workshop March/April 2021. • IAOA President Laure Vieu gave a talk during the 1st OntoCommons Horizontal Workshop. • Co-organization of the FOMI 2021 workshop in September 2021. • Discussion with co-chairs of the IAOA Industry and Standards Technical Committee for the organization of events in the coming years. • OntoCommons will liaise with IAOA to utilise their outputs.
14	IDSA - International Data Spaces Association	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TEKNIKER (part of the OntoCommons consortium) is a member. • OntoCommons will liaise with IDSA to utilise their outputs and contribute to their groups.
15	iiRDS – The International Standard for intelligent	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The iiRDS ontology can be harmonised and made interoperable with the other ontologies involved in the OntoCommons project (e.g., EMMO, DOLCE, BFO). • iiRDS has become an OntoCommons demonstrator with a use case that aims to enrich technical documentation

	information Request and Delivery	<p>content with iiRDS metadata to enable the digital representation of documentation in industry 4.0 scenarios.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • iiRDS will provide insights and recommendations to shape the OntoCommons Roadmap. • Members of iiRDS attended an OntoCommons webinar and a session of the 1st OntoCommons Horizontal Workshop. • OntoCommons is liaising with iiRDS to discuss the technical potential of the different Ontology levels. • Members of iiRDS have applied to the StandICT.eu Open calls to help support the work they are doing with iiRDS. Should the application be successful they will provide content that will contribute to the OntoCommons.eu roadmap. • OntoCommons will liaise with iiRDS to utilise their outputs.
16	INCITS - InterNational Committee Information Technology Standards for	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hedi Karray (OntoCommons technical coordinator) is a member. • OntoCommons will liaise with INCITS to utilise their outputs.
17	IOF - Industrial Ontology Foundry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • OntoCommons is contributing to the development of a standardised set of open industrial ontologies that spans the entire domain of traditional manufacturing. • Members of the OntoCommons EAB are members of the Industry Ontology Foundry (Barry Smith, Boonserm Kulvatunyou). • Dimitris Kiritsis, WP1 leader, is one of the IOF Technical Oversight Board vice chairs. • Hedi Karray, OntoCommons technical coordinator, is member of the IOF Technical Oversight Board. • The IOF Working Group is developing the ZDM (Zero Defects Manufacturing) ontology, related to quality improvement and that could be implemented by some of the OntoCommons demonstrators. • OntoCommons will use the IOF core as the MLO for OntoCommons.

18	ISO - International Organization for Standardization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Hedi Karray is collaborating with ISO/TC 184/SC4. Fahad Khan, Markus Stumptner, David Price attended the TLO/MLO workshop in March/April 2021. OntoCommons is considering the involvement (supported by Barry Smith, member of EAB) in ISO/IEC JTC 1 in particular the working group concerned with top-level ontology standards. OntoCommons will liaise with ISO to utilise their outputs.
19	Mat-o-Lab	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Members of Mat-o-Lab attended the OntoCommons Doric event on 7th June 2021. OntoCommons is liaising with Mat-o-Lab to discuss a possible cooperation. OntoCommons will liaise with Mat-o-Lab to utilise their outputs, in particular Matportal.
20	MTConnect Institute	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The MTConnect Standard is the leading CNC ANSI standard, currently deployed on over 100,000 machines globally for IIoT data. They have been collaborating with the IOF OntoCommons members in a joint working group to define observation and device capabilities as ontological terms.
21	NCOR - National Center for Ontology Research	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> NCOR is headed by Barry Smith, EAB member of OntoCommons. Hedi Karray, OntoCommons technical coordinator, is associate researcher at NCOR. OntoCommons will liaise with NCOR to utilise their outputs.
22	NIST - National Institute of Standards and Technology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Members of NIST attended both OntoCommons Doric event on 15th of March 2021 and 7th June 2021. Serm Kulvatunyou gave a talk during the 1st OntoCommons Horizontal Workshop. OntoCommons will liaise with NIST to utilise their outputs.
23	OGC - Open GeoSpatial Consortium	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> First contact initiated Collaboration scope not defined yet
24	OISPG - Open Innovation Strategy and Policy Group	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> OISPG is part of the Industry Commons Foundation (OntoCommons consortium).

25	oneM2M - Standards for M2M and the Internet of Things	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> UPM is a member of oneM2M oneM2M is interested in joining the OntoCommons Focus Area "Cooperation on Standardisation" as both oneM2M and OntoCommons are interested in semantic interoperability.
26	OISPG - Open Innovation Strategy and Policy Group	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> OISPG takes part into the Industry Commons Steering Board, and it is reviving its activities in conjunction with long term sustainability for OntoCommons.
27	OPC Foundation - The Industrial Interoperability Standard TM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> OPC Foundation has expressed interest in joining the OntoCommons Focus Area "Cooperation on Standardisation", where OPC Foundation can support and provide suggestions in this area
28	OPEN INDUSTRY ALLIANCE 4.0	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> First contact initiated Collaboration scope not defined yet
29	PCA - POSC Caesar Association	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ICF is in contact to revive the activities of PCA in conjunction with long term sustainability for OntoCommons.
30	RDA - Research Data Alliance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> OntoCommons gave a presentation about the project during RDA's 17th Plenary Meeting in April 2021. RDA proposes to provide support to identify and get in contact with the relevant stakeholders with the RDA galaxy of Interest Groups and Working Groups. The OntoCommons multi-stakeholder collaboration Knowledge Exchange Space (KExS) already involves Interest Groups interested in ontologies such as the RDA Chemistry IG and the Vocabulary and Semantic Service IG. RDA will help OntoCommons to identify the relevant recommendations for the project and its stakeholders. OntoCommons is considering to create an RDA Community of practice for data documentation in materials and manufacturing. OntoCommons is considering to create an Industry Commons group within RDA. OntoCommons will liaise with RDA to utilise their outputs.
31	SSHOCRo	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> First contact initiated

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collaboration scope not defined yet
32	StandICT.eu	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • OntoCommons.eu will provide key insights on appropriate and pertinent gaps, recommendations and priorities in ICT Standardisation around ontologies for StandICT.eu's future Open Calls. • OntoCommons.eu may publicise the opportunities offered to its stakeholders by the StandICT.eu Open Calls and encourage applications. • OntoCommons.eu may also take part in webinars and events organised by StandICT.eu 2023 and vice versa. • StandICT.eu is about to launch a new Technical Working Group on Ontologies which will include experts from OntoCommons.eu and ultimately yield a Gaps Analysis Report for ICT standardisation activities in the Ontology domain and generate timely and pertinent content to feed directly into the StandICT.eu EUOS. (European Standards Observatory)
33	TDWG	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TDWG has been invited to participate as an expert in the OntoCommons Standardisation focus area. TDWG can support this section and provide feedback. • Potential collaboration in the StandICT Technical Working Group (TWG) on ontologies. • Involvement in the establishment of the technical principles.
34	UK National Digital Twin Programme	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • OntoCommons is using UK National Digital Twin Programme's resources. • UK National Digital Twin Programme members attended the OntoCommons TLO/MLO workshop. • OntoCommons will liaise with the UK National Digital Twin Programme to utilise their outputs.
35	W3C - World Wide Web Consortium	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • UPM (OntoCommons consortium) is involved in W3C groups. • OntoCommons will liaise with the W3C to utilise their outputs.
36	Semantic Treehouse	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • OntoCommons can join the Semantic Treehouse Discord community to get support, shared ideas and inspiration
37	IUPAC – International Union	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This is the standards organisation in chemistry and governance for the IUPAC Goldbook, which in turn is the

	of pure and applied chemistry	<p>basis for OntoCommons related ontology development (i.e., expressing a standard in an ontology).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> IUPAC “joined” OntoCommons through RDA (RDA Chemistry IG).
38	OPENNEXT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The initiative looks at changing the way products are manufactured using the power of open source. One of OPENNEXT outputs is a 'Library of Open-Source Hardware' (LOSH), a distributed open knowledge base to make open-source hardware searchable among different platforms, for which the project has been developing an ontology based on the Open-KnowHow specification: OntoCommons and OPENNECT could start a collaboration and support each other.

Table 5 - List of relevant initiatives in the NMBP standardisation area